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Disinformation on social networks in Spanish and Portuguese Iberian digital media ecosystem

Report

Deliverable — D3.1

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Deliverable Task Leader(s): Javier Huertas Tato (Universidad Politécnica de Madrid, UPM)

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Coordinator

Partners

Associate

List of participants

Participant	Partner Institution
Universidad Politécnica de Madrid	
Huertas-Tato, Javier	UPM
Panizo-Lledot, Ángel	UPM
Camacho, David	UPM
Barcelona Supercomputing Center	
Carolina, Belver	BSC
Philippe, Olivier	BSC
Devlin, Summer	BSC
Rosas, Claudia	BSC
Universidad de Granada	
Gómez Romero, Juan	UGR
Molina Solana, Miguel	UGR
Laboratório de Instrumentação e Física Experimental de Partículas	
Vranič, Ana	LIP
Almeida, Paulo	LIP
Gonçalves-Sá, Joana	LIP
Universidad de Navarra	
Salaverría, Ramón	UNAV
Sánchez-Hualde, Anais	UNAV

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1. Introduction

The aim of this technical report is twofold and hybrid: Discovery and analysis of *misinformation spread patterns* in Online Social Networks (OSNs), and development of *technologies able to track* this aforementioned phenomenon. Practical applications of developed tools will help report on misinformation spread. We show both dimensions of this: results and methods.

Our object of study comprises three different topics: *Covid-19, Climate change, and Gender issues*. Each explores a different area of interest for European action. Covid-19, though dated, is a plentiful source of *medical* misinformation, readily available. Climate change is a pressing issue, as global average temperature rises, popular consensus on this topic becomes critical and the ability to quickly identify narratives and stances becomes extremely relevant. to be able to quickly identify Understanding the misinformation spread might offer insights on how to stop it and properly educate about a critical topic. Finally, Gender-related disinformation is applied to spread a hate-speech message too; understanding the spread might offer insight on hate-speech dissemination patterns by proxy.

1.1. Context

Misinformation came into the spotlight during the Covid-19 pandemic and has been present in public discourse ever-since. However, misinformation is not a new phenomenon, for example the misplaced assumption of ‘vaccine side effects’ dates back to Andrew Wakefield’s 1998 article about the MMR vaccine. This pseudoscientific publication misled a large portion of the population to erringly believe there is a causality relation between vaccines and autism, a fact that is still relevant as it is continuously reinforced in the fear-speech recently seen in the U.S.. Other scientific facts, like climate change, are called into question. By 2019 there has been observed a *100% agreement* of the scientific community on anthropogenic climate change (Powell 2017), which makes anthropogenic climate change denial especially jarring. Even more outlandish claims are made and become widespread, ranging from harmless crackpot theories like flat earth conspiracies, to actual national security threats like the Q-Anon conspiracy.

How can these *evidently wrong* facts become so popular? Online Social Networks play a pivotal role in the distribution of *any* kind of information. This includes both: the *harmful* and *harmless*. While earlier forms of misinformation had to travel physically through paper print or on a mouth-to-mouth basis, nowadays we can distribute messages globally (and *massively*) without barely any effort. There is a relevant keyword here: ‘Distribution’: as information travels and spreads, it leaves a trail of messages that can hypothetically be traced down. These trails form a network that shows exactly *how* accounts work together to distribute misinformation through a social media platform.

However, tracking this trail is challenging. Information often moves beyond social media e.g. through traditional media outlets, non-network digital media or word of mouth, transference is done through non-structured means. For example, imagine you

see a post on Twitter/X, then write about it without ever interacting with the earlier post. How do we track this information? Is it even possible?

In addition, the internet is progressively becoming a network of ‘walled gardens’¹ which makes tracking misinformation between social media platforms even harder. In addition, social media platforms are slowly turning into ‘crippleware’². Most platforms do not provide the kind of public access needed to analyze content in sufficient detail to track misinformation while those that allow access often impose paywalls beyond the reach of many academic institutions. While initiatives like the Digital Services Act (DSA, detailed in **Annex 1**) may help address this challenge in the future, *for now* we must rely on workarounds to uncover how interactions on social media actually unfolds.

Ironically, now, more than ever, it has become a pressing issue to understand the dynamics of misinformation spread. While technological works frequently focus on misinformation at a content level (like discerning whether something is misinformation or not), the actual dynamics of spread have been disregarded alongside with the nature of the spread information, i.e. by accepting or refusing certain news or content.

Properly studying and understanding social network misinformation spread dynamics is core to *national security*, *media literacy* and more crucial challenges Europe has to face in this latest decade. As technological institutions, our approach is eminently technical, making use of existing cutting edge techniques, as well as newly developed algorithms to help us characterize the dissemination of misinformation online. We have technological challenges to overcome in order to properly analyse this phenomena from a data science perspective.

1.2. Tech challenges

To conduct this report we needed to overcome existing limitations in the state of the art. We have briefly hinted at the nature of these issues beforehand. To summarize, two main technical challenges have been found: a) Datasets of user-generated content are now exceedingly scarce within the current OSN ecosystem. b) There is a lack of metadata-rich datasets that enable straightforward tracking of information as it spreads across a social media platform.

There is some overlap between both challenges. For example, the scarcity of data means that metadata-rich datasets are harder to come by. However, we treat them as two separate phenomena that we find solutions for independently.

Challenge 1: Data scarcity. As more companies lock their data behind unreasonable paywalls (even for researchers) data has become scarce. During development of this report we pondered on several alternatives. Twitter/X has steep prices for the amounts

¹ A “walled garden” is a common tech term, it denotes that users cannot access the data of a given service.

² “Crippleware” refers to software that has been deliberately downgraded, excluding vital functionality, until the user pays for it. Twitter/X access to data to researchers has been subject to this phenomenon, for example.

of data needed. Meta is strictly inaccessible, being very protective of their data. Youtube deals mostly with video, which is considerably harder to trace, on top of having steep daily limits for free users. Same goes with TikTok; on top of the technical difficulty, it also offers an opaque endpoint (a specific web address where apps request and exchange information or services) that's hard to freely work with. Reddit followed in the footsteps of Twitter/X and restricted access to their data too. So far, we have mentioned some of the major platforms found online, discarding them one by one. To operate with data we need to freely access the message-content data, or have a functional endpoint to a well-maintained search engine; neither of these platforms offer these strictly necessary functionalities at a reasonable price. Therefore, the largest platforms have to be discarded immediately. Other, smaller platforms do comply with our pre-requisites for the analysis, however, they lack something crucial to our report: Portuguese or Spanish communities. The lack of hispanic or lusophonic speakers in platforms such as Bluesky or Mastodon make them ineligible to study our target languages.

Solution 1: Telegram. Telegram is a glaring omission from the challenge description. It is the only network that allows for widespread data acquisition. It works like Whatsapp (another Meta product) but has an available public endpoint that lets us connect directly to the chats and gather the necessary information for disinformation tracking purposes. We crawl the network from some seed channels, recovering as many messages as possible. This network links to the next channel³. As interactions between messages are not explicit, they require to be discovered in some way. Overall, Telegram stands as the best alternative to study misinformation spread.

However, this platform presents another challenge: Telegram does not produce metadata that enables straightforward tracking of messages across the network. Unlike other platforms, such as X (formerly Twitter), where propagation can be easily studied, Telegram provides far less information.

Challenge 2: Metadata-rich data. In order to study propagation dynamics across social media, it is necessary to have links that relate pieces of information. For example, X/Twitter has resposts, quotations and responses, which lead to self-evident relationships as users explicitly interact with content. These metadata act as edges for social graphs, in other words, as the relation two pieces of information share. We can, then, travel from message to message following the trace of interactions users left. X/Twitter was the ideal platform to study this kind of dynamics as these relationships were extremely abundant and easy to obtain. Thus, when we study social media propagation dynamics, we need a way to find links between informational pieces. These have been traditionally found via metadata generated from explicit interactions in the platform, without the need to infer any kind of link. Metadata-rich data that allows tracking a piece of information in a straightforward way have been a cornerstone of this field of study. While this is still possible using legacy databases (old data downloaded before the lockdown) we are no longer able to study propagation on more modern trends. Walled garden policies have rendered many techniques unfeasible for research centers.

³ The algorithm is detailed in section 6.1.

Solution 2: Link inference. Our proposal, used in this report, begins by understanding the following: even in databases with annotated relationships, information propagates in spurious ways. For example, following the old X/Twitter approach, any user could read another tweet and plagiarize its contents. This relationship would have never been taken into consideration, as per the database, it was nonexistent. In some particular scenarios, information is propagated through offline means like word of mouth, along with offsite means like chat conversations. Understanding that propagation can happen within non-explicit channels, allows us to try and infer these relationships.

Recent advances in Natural Language Processing have allowed the academic community to analyse text via similarity. This core idea that two pieces of similar content share a high score, can be applied in cases like the aforementioned plagiarism scenario among others. Similarity-based relationships, in our experience, have been partially ineffective when plainly applied, requiring several adjustment steps to represent high-quality information cascades.

Therefore, the proposed solution to the omission of relationship data is finding similarity-informed relationships. Our report and study rely on these similarity-based techniques.

Challenge 3: Integrative Analysis. As mentioned, Twitter/X has made academic access very costly. However, given its still significant use and historical data, it is still a relevant platform. Moreover, there has been little cross-national analysis, leveraging multi-lingual platforms.

Solution 3: Comparison Across Platforms. As a source of misinformation claims, we used the GlobalClaims⁴ dataset (Vranić et al.). This collection of multi-country, multi-lingual fact-checked claims provides the veracity classification, thematic classification across 22 subtopics, and original URL, facilitating social media analysis.

1.3. Objectives

Within this report we aim to fulfill several objectives. The main objective stemming every other point is the following: Analyze social media propagation in the hispanic/lusophonic ecosystem.

Objective 1 → *Overcome technical challenges to study propagation without explicit interaction data.* This high-level objective represents the *technological* part of the report, comprising all the techniques necessary to achieve a high quality study.

Objective 1.1 → *Obtain large amounts of data from Telegram.* After initial screenings, Telegram lacks a proper interface to access all information at once, the only solution is the mass access and storage of messages in local repositories.

Objective 1.2 → *Algorithmic recovery of common hoaxes in the wild.* Using all information available, recover hoaxes to be studied under the selected topics. These

⁴ <https://doi.org/10.1145/3746275.3762201>

are: Covid-19, Climate change, Gender-related. Available databases contain several usable hoaxes, such as the IBERIFIER Plus database.

Objective 1.3 → *Develop a semantic-informed linking algorithm.* One of the keystones of this report is the novelty of the approach. This means developing novel techniques from scratch, as well as adapting existing techniques for this analysis.

Objective 2 → *Topic analysis of target domains.* Evaluating every subject of disinformation is unfeasible, our report is constrained to a subset of target topics that require some rationale. Sub-objectives represent each target domain. We have opted to spread our analysis across several domains, including sample topics that may help understand several patterns. We focus on misinformation hotbeds, topics where misinformation has proven to be extremely virulent.

Objective 2.1 → *Explore mass messages based on topic.* Offering a visualization of the topic helps contextualize further results. A study can be conducted on messages to view the separation of discourse by thematic/narrative influence.

Objective 2.2 → *Analyze misinformation propagation in health issues.* The chosen topic for this task is observing Covid-19 disinformation. The global pandemic is an old topic by now, however it is very convenient. 1) It helps us validate our analysis by comparing it to previous topics. 2) There is still panic about vaccines and other Covid-adjacent issues ongoing. 3) Data on Covid-19 is plentiful and well-known, therefore it's a perfect control-case.

Objective 2.3 → *Analyze misinformation propagation in environmental issues.* For this objective we will use Climate Change. Unlike Covid-19, it has not been some time-localized event, instead it has been ongoing for several decades. There is a pressing need for environmental action, and the continued misinformation has been a rock in the way since its discovery; thus the choice.

Objective 2.4 → *Analyze misinformation propagation in social issues.* Finally, we observe gender-related issues, LGBTQI+ social issues. Again, acceptance of non-normative collectives has been a perennial societal challenge. In this regard, education is a key component of combating societal inequality and misinformation is one of their biggest threats. Therefore, understanding the dynamics of misinformation woven with hate speech is fundamental for development.

Objective 3 → *Apply developed techniques to practical chosen domains.* This is fairly straightforward. Using the results from Objectives 1 and 2 we expect to properly analyze misinformation propagation.

Objective 3.1 → *Examine misinformation cascades on chosen hoaxes.* Using the linking algorithm, we can obtain cascades that can be observed and analyzed. The result of this objective is a practical examination on how misinformation is spread.

Objective 3.2 → *Examine misinformation actors and influence over cascades.* Given several cascades, it is possible to examine details like: who influences who? Which

channel acts as an authority on a given topic? Is influence evenly distributed?. These questions can be explored in full using the provided cascades and checking the targeted misinformation channels (forums of discussion).

Objective 3.3 → *Examine actors and stances over disinformation narratives.* Cross OSNs retrieving data from multiple sources to detect who supports who. Is this revealing of actors intentions? How does stance evolve over time?

Objective 4 → *Offer a comparison of fact-checked claims across platforms*

Objective 4.1 → *Extract large amounts of data from Twitter/X.* Take advantage of an existing large and curated dataset of fact checked claims. Focus on claims in Spanish and Portuguese, on Covid19 and environmental issues. Identify which of those claims circulated on Twitter/X.

Objective 4.2 → *Analyze temporal dynamics of false information spread.* From the identified claims, create sharing cascades and cascade distributions and describe the hoax frequency over time.

Objective 4.3 → *Compare frequency and topics across platforms and countries.* Identify common hoaxes between Twitter/X and Telegram, in Portugal, Spain, Latin America and Brazil, using automatic similarity methods (including fuzzy matching).

Overall, this develops our objectives, which we will fulfill across the document.

2. Topic analysis for visualization

In this section we will analyse the hoaxes identified on Telegram, produced by each search, as well as the found affected channels. Each topic is analyzed within their own subsection.

2.1 Covid-19 hoaxes and actors

We present the hoaxes found in Table 1, while associated channels are in Table 2. Keep in mind our algorithms are language-agnostic. Inputs can detect cascades in any language.

Table 1. Covid-19 Hoaxes. In Spanish

N	Hoax
1	Antes era la pandemia, ahora la guerra: los desinformadores se transforman con el conflicto de Ucrania
2	Bill Gates no ha admitido en este vídeo que la vacunación fue un "terrible error"
3	Bill Gates no ha dicho que va a inyectar vacunas anticovid-19 al ganado
4	Cuidado con el vídeo sobre el positivo en COVID-19 de la reina Isabel II que incluye una imagen de la ivermectina: no hay pruebas de que lo esté tomando y la cadena que lo emitió asegura que fue un error
5	Cuidado con los vídeos de hombres que dicen haber hecho el cambio de sexo registral "de un día para otro" para "beneficiarse" de la ley trans
6	El Parlamento español no suprimió el uso de mascarillas en interiores
7	El vídeo de Anthony Fauci sobre el no uso de mascarillas: está recortado y en realidad dice que se equivocó al no recomendarlas al inicio de la pandemia con lo que se sabe en 2023
8	En España no se alcanzaron 50 grados hace ya más de medio siglo
9	Es falso que la vacuna contra la covid-19 produzca "decenas de miles de muertos", como se asegura en una revista
10	Es falso que los Cuerpos de Seguridad del Estado y los jueces no fueran vacunados contra la covid-19
11	España no ha retirado la vacuna de Astrazeneca, al contrario de lo que afirma un tuit viral
12	Grafeno en las vacunas: cómo la mentira que nos convierte en un imán ha recorrido el mundo
13	La OMS no afirma que la pandemia se alargará por la vacuna de la covid-19 sino por la desigualdad en su reparto
14	La enfermedad de la covid-19 sí es nueva, al contrario de lo que indica el grupo Biólogos por la Verdad
15	La teoría conspirativa de los 'chemtrails': preguntas y respuestas
16	Las afirmaciones falsas sobre el 5G y la COVID-19 del vídeo de Thomas Cowan
17	Las falsedades del nobel Giaever para negar las evidencias del cambio climático
18	Las muertes cardiovasculares entre atletas profesionales no se han duplicado cada tres meses en 2021 por la vacuna
19	Las vacunas contra la COVID-19 no causan muertes repentinas, a diferencia de lo que afirma el documental viral "Died Suddenly"
20	Las vacunas de la covid-19 no causan "efectos autodestructivos" en el cuerpo
21	Los artículos que alertan de que más del 82% de las embarazadas vacunadas sufrirán abortos se basan en un estudio erróneo
22	Los documentos sobre la vacuna de Pfizer publicados por la FDA no desvelan efectos secundarios hasta ahora silenciados
23	Los laboratorios ucranianos financiados por los Estados Unidos no son para crear armas biológicas, sino para detectar la aparición de amenazas relacionadas con virus o bacterias
24	Los niños vacunados de covid no tienen 52 veces más probabilidades de morir
25	Los test PCR sí son una prueba diagnóstica
26	Mentiras antivacunas: así han intentado que realizáramos inmunizarnos en 2021
27	No es cierto que las mascarillas causen enfermedades neurodegenerativas incurables
28	No es ilegal vacunar a los niños contra la covid-19
29	No, Israel no ha dejado el EuroMOMO ni los datos reflejan un incremento alarmante de exceso de mortalidad tras la campaña de vacunación contra la COVID-19
30	No, Sanidad no ha "admitido" que 14 lotes de vacunas provocaron 200 muertos en España: cómo interpretar los informes de farmacovigilancia
31	No, la Unión Europea no ha lanzado "pasaportes sanitarios obligatorios" ni los no vacunados van a ser "excluidos de la sociedad"
32	No, no ha ingresado un niño de 10 años en la UCI del Hospital Virgen de la Arrixaca (Murcia) por un "infarto de miocardio" tras vacunarse contra la COVID-19
33	Nos preguntáis si España ha disparado la compra de gas a Rusia este verano
34	Pfizer no comercializó la vacuna de la covid sin comprobar su eficacia
35	Qué es la Agenda 2030 y qué dicen los bulos virales que desinforman sobre este plan impulsado por la ONU
36	Qué sabemos del vídeo de un supuesto ejecutivo de Pfizer reconociendo que la farmacéutica está "dirigiendo" la evolución del SARS-CoV-2
37	Rezar frente a una clínica abortiva no está prohibido, como afirma Catalán (UPN), pero puede ser delito si deriva en acoso
38	Trudeau no afirmó que seguirá aplicando medidas inconstitucionales contra la covid
39	¿Qué sabemos sobre los '17 fallecimientos de ancianos tras vacunarse' en una residencia de Yecla (Murcia)? Las muertes se produjeron debido a un brote de COVID-19 y no por la vacuna, según la residencia y la Consejería de Sanidad de Murcia
40	"Elon Musk me echó de Twitter": el meme que se viraliza como real en la red social

These hoaxes make up for the queries that will later be addressed in visualization. Furthermore, we found these channels affected by the hoaxes.

Table 2. Covid-19 Channels.

N	Channel	N	Channel
1	ellocodelacorralachannel	13	exponiendolaverdadoculta
2	chemtrailsaquintacolumna	14	infoburbuja
3	conscienciaterraplana	15	EIContrafuerte
4	laquintacolumnainternational	16	ejercitoremamente
5	Somosrealistas	17	elinvestigador_org
6	supercontagiadores	18	EIDiestro
7	covidland_espanol	19	PLANDEMIA_MUNDIAL_COVID
8	medicosporlaverdadar	20	PADRESPORLAVERDAD
9	LARECONQUISTA_ESP	21	medicosporlaverdadESP
10	paremosNewOrdenMundial	22	cienciaycovid
11	rafapalreal	23	ExponiendoLaElite
12	InfoVacunas		

From the hoaxes, several observations can be found. First, our method aims to be mostly automatic. Automation is prone to errors, which we aim to illustrate along with the positive results. In this screening, the automatic extraction yields some results unrelated to the at-hand topic; for example, Hoax 8 is about Climate Change instead of Covid-19, Hoax 40 is X/Twitter criticism, and so on.

The rest of the hoaxes play off several Covid-19 related issues like vaccines or masks. These are mostly examples of fearmongering, usually with the double objective of demeaning treatment effectiveness, as well as criticizing institutions. Points frequently mentioned are PCR tests, Vaccines and Masks; all science-backed or government-appointed effective methods of viral contention are harshly criticized. Hoaxes in these categories denote overwhelming distrust in official institutions, even the European Union at large. The origin of this distrust is unclear.

Though the presence of some channels could be seen as accidental, the affected channels have overlap with the topics. It is interesting to see channels like 'conscienciaterraplana', a flat-earth channel, focusing on crossing topics like Covid-19. Channels usually prefer to self-present as science-backed critical thinkers that go against the current consensus (cienciaycovid, somosrealistas, etc). Others have nationalistic hints, such as 'LARECONQUISTA_ESP' or 'ejercitoremamente'. There's also some channels that pose as legitimate news outlets posing for genuine information (EIContrafuerte, EIDiestro).

Visualizations have been extracted from all hoaxes, however, for the sake of clarity and correctness, we hand-pick three. Hoaxes 4, 9 and 34 show different graphs worth evaluating. Keep in mind that the graphs produced by our algorithms are still fed into the influence analysis, maintaining our end-to-end approach to automated analysis.

2.2 Climate change hoaxes and actors

We present the hoaxes found in Table 3. Compared to Covid-19, misinformation is more prevalent across time, thus many more disinformation can be found on this topic, thus the increased number.

Table 3. Climate change hoaxes. In spanish & portuguese

N	Hoax
1	No hay un "brote mortal" de malaria en Estados Unidos provocado por Bill Gates
2	Von der Leyen no pide comprar petróleo ruso para "salvar a Europa de Putin"
3	A Amazônia é o pulmão da Terra? Não, a ciência já o desmentiu
4	Una nevada "única" en Estados Unidos no significa que no exista el cambio climático
5	Greta Thunberg no hizo un llamado a tener guerras más sostenibles, es un «deepfake»
6	No hay registro de que el papa Francisco y Bill Clinton hayan pedido una «despoblación urgente» para salvar el planeta
7	Número de glaciares no mundo permanece igual desde o nascimento de Guterres?
8	La ganadería española cumple con la normativa europea, pero no reduce las emisiones de GEI desde hace más de una década
9	Gasolineiras absorveram parte da descida do ISP na margem bruta? Dados apurados indicam que não
10	Mapas de previsão meteorológica estão a ser alterados para criar alarmismo climático?
11	É falso. Temperaturas baixas no Texas ou gelo no deserto não provam "arrefecimento global"
12	União Europeia recuou na decisão de banir carros novos com motores de combustão a partir de 2035?
13	Lido no Facebook: "Cem empresas são responsáveis por 70% das emissões globais de CO2"
14	Impuestos, sueldos y cambio climático: los datos falsos y verdaderos de los debates de Baleares
15	El vídeo de Bill Gates "cortando una entrevista" sobre vacunas es falso y expertos señalan que está hecho con IA
16	China no está aumentando su consumo de carbón debido a la construcción de paneles solares
17	El documento "firmado por más de 1.600 científicos" sobre la emergencia climática: contexto y afirmaciones desinformadoras
18	Las falsedades del nobel Gjaever para negar las evidencias del cambio climático
19	La Comisión Europea no ha anunciado "restricciones de agua para toda la población" ante la situación de sequía
20	El CO2 causa el calentamiento global, aunque respirarlo no afecte a la salud de las personas (título bueno)
21	La Agenda 2030 no es una maniobra de EEUU para someter al mundo
22	Cómo sabemos que el co2 sí causa el cambio climático
23	Lê-se no Facebook: "Principal fator de influência nas alterações climáticas é o Sol e não os gases atmosféricos"
24	Importações asseguram "60,7% do consumo energético europeu", destaca-se no Facebook
25	Líder do Fórum Económico Mundial defende abate de cães e gatos para combater as alterações climáticas?
26	El sello de la rana de Rainforest Alliance en alimentos no indica que contengan insectos
27	El origen del petróleo sí es fósil (aunque no viene solamente de la descomposición de los dinosaurios)
28	Es engañoso decir que el origen de los incendios sea que los agricultores no estén autorizados a "limpiar el bosque"
29	El Foro Económico Mundial no ha ordenado a los gobiernos "arrestar" a los negacionistas del cambio climático
30	No, esta foto de la NASA no muestra las nevadas actuales en Canadá y Estados Unidos: es de 2002
31	Alega-se no Facebook: Tirando a lenha e o carvão vegetal, "não existem combustíveis fósseis"
32	No solo es "la opinión" de expertos: cómo la comunidad científica llegó a un acuerdo respecto al origen del cambio climático
33	Que el mayor récord por calor en el planeta se produjera en 1913 no significa que el calentamiento global no exista
34	Un eventual enfriamiento del Sol no revertiría los efectos del calentamiento global
35	Por qué la nueva norma de la UE sobre microplásticos no prohíbe los campos de fútbol de césped artificial
36	Greta Thunberg no obligó a unos manifestantes a dejar de respirar por el clima
37	Nubes, estelas, radares y lámparas: no son fotos de manipulaciones ocultas del clima
38	El deshielo de Groenlandia ni es natural ni se está revirtiendo
39	No provocan incendios desde helicópteros para culpar al cambio climático
40	No, Repsol no está ofreciendo inversiones en petróleo y gas: suplantaron a El Mundo y al presidente de la empresa para colártela
41	Nobel da Física provou que não existe aquecimento global? As alegações não têm fundamento científico
42	No son falsas víctimas ucranianas sino manifestantes contra el cambio climático
43	Es falso que España y 12 países más hayan firmado un acuerdo para abolir la agricultura por el cambio climático
44	El fundador del Foro Económico Mundial no escribió un libro con un plan para "eliminar" a 4.000 millones de personas hacia 2050
45	Fecho da refinaria de Matosinhos teve impacto nos "stocks" de gasóleo?
46	Filipinas no ha ordenado el arresto de Bill Gates por las vacunas contra la covid, se trata de un bulo
47	Es engañoso que las emisiones de gases de efecto invernadero hayan caído un 14 % en los últimos cuatro años
48	Imagens da Terra e da Lua divulgadas pela NASA provam que "o espaço é 'fake'", garante-se nas redes sociais
49	Manual para que no te cuelen desinformación durante la Cumbre del Clima COP28
50	El enviado de EE.UU. para el clima no habló de sacrificar a millones de humanos para salvar al planeta
51	Não, o termo "aquecimento global" não foi substituído pela expressão "alterações climáticas"
52	Prisão de Greta Thunberg em protesto na Alemanha "foi encenada"?
53	Data and Disinformation about the Spanish Minister Teresa Ribera, the Falcon jet, and her Bike Arrival to a Climate Meeting in Valladolid
54	El timo de las falsas inversiones en petróleo que usa caras conocidas para colártela
55	La Comisión Europea no ha dicho que vaya a «preparar restricciones de agua» para toda la población
56	Gelo na Antártida está a expandir-se e por isso não existe aquecimento global?
57	El CO2 antropogénico es la causa del calentamiento global, aunque su cantidad en la atmósfera sea pequeña
58	¿Cómo sabemos que el cambio climático actual no es igual que el 'Óptimo Climático Medieval'?
59	Greta Thunberg no ha pedido que se usen las centrales nucleares
60	La UE no ha pedido que la población deje de desayunar como medida para preservar el medio ambiente
61	La NASA no ha demostrado que la ganadería en Argentina no contamina

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N	Hoax
62	Los estudios que avalan el consenso científico sobre el origen antropogénico del cambio climático también incluyen análisis escépticos
63	Não, "sistema HAARP" não é responsável pelas alterações climáticas
64	El rápido calentamiento global es inducido por el hombre y no por el Sol y la Luna
65	La desinformación que usa los colores del mapa del tiempo de TVE para negar el cambio climático
66	No, Bill Gates no es el nieto del filántropo y asesor original de la Fundación Rockefeller, Frederick Taylor Gates: es un bulo
67	Alega-se nas redes sociais: "Aquecimento global é uma fraude"
68	Consenso sobre intervenção humana na origem do aquecimento global é de apenas 0,3%?
69	No, este vídeo de Bill Gates en el que se rehúsa a continuar una entrevista no es real: es un vídeo manipulado
70	Não, aumento da extensão de gelo marinho no Ártico não significa uma inversão da tendência
71	Bill Gates no pronosticó el brote de viruela del mono
72	El cambio climático influye en los incendios forestales, aunque no es el único factor responsable
73	Que existan patentes registradas sobre modificación climática no significa que funcionen (ni que modifiquen el clima)
74	La gráfica climática del palo de hockey, que representa un aumento de las temperaturas sin precedentes a partir del siglo XX, es fiable
75	La Unión Europea no ha votado en contra de un alto al fuego en Gaza
76	El CO2 de la atmósfera producido por los seres humanos es un pequeño porcentaje del total, pero suficiente para provocar una crisis climática
77	En 1961 y 2021 se registró la misma temperatura media, pero eso no niega el cambio climático
78	Bill Gates no ha dicho que va a inyectar vacunas anticovid-19 al ganado
79	Cuidado con la comparación sin contexto entre el uso de combustible de un avión y una explotación ganadera
80	No, Greta Thunberg no ha pedido usar "misiles biodegradables" ni "granadas veganas": el vídeo está manipulado
81	Qué sabemos sobre el cartel publicitario que dice "¿Futuro, o asesino del clima?" en alemán
82	Que aumenten los bosques no significa que no exista la deforestación
83	Qué dice y qué no dice el estudio sobre el aumento de hielo en zonas de la Antártida y por qué no significa que la crisis climática no sea real
84	La ley de cambio climático no prohíbe explorar minas de tierras raras
85	Qué sabemos sobre la detención del 'influencer' Andrew Tate y el papel de sus interacciones en redes sociales con Greta Thunberg
86	Contas do IUC. Automóvel que emite 148 gramas de CO2 por quilómetro paga "imposto de quase 700 euros"?
87	El Parlamento Europeo no ha pedido «prohibir» las vacunas covid
88	Las emisiones de CO2 de España y Estados Unidos están bajando, pero esto no demuestra que haya un "alarmismo climático"
89	Esta imagem mostra cartazes deixados no chão por estudantes que protestam contra as alterações climáticas?
90	Los bulos virales en torno a las protestas por la reforma de las pensiones en Francia
91	Dados da NASA revelam que "a temperatura média da Terra baixou desde 2016"?
92	Combustíveis fósseis. É falso que a Rússia tenha faturado mais 158% nos últimos dois meses do que no mesmo período em 2021
93	Las predicciones de subida del nivel del mar no han fallado, como asegura un podcast viral
94	La Unión Europea no ha puesto fin al cobro de la maleta de mano en los aviones
95	Empresa financiada por Bill Gates é responsável por surgimento de casos de malária nos EUA?
96	La teoría conspirativa de los 'chemtrails': preguntas y respuestas
97	Bill Gates no ha "pronosticado" que la próxima pandemia tendrá lugar en 2025 ni que esta será provocada por el virus "SEERS"
98	No, Antena 3 no ha usado el rótulo "el cambio climático provoca nevadas por el norte"
99	A NASA mente e "os satélites são um mito" pois não resistiriam às altas temperaturas no espaço?
100	No son políticos de la UE que festejen sus privilegios en la Eurocámara
101	Parlamento Europeu tem proposta de "taxa ambiental" de 20 cêntimos sobre "todos os produtos com embalagem"?
102	Diz-se no Facebook: É "mentira" que alterações climáticas possam afetar saúde cardiovascular
103	Los terremotos no pueden afectar al clima
104	Foi emitido um mandado de prisão dirigido a Bill Gates nas Filipinas?
105	No, Bill Clinton y el Papa Francisco no han pedido una "despoblación urgente" para salvar el planeta
106	Vídeo do TikTok em que Bill Gates abandona entrevista é verdadeiro?
107	No, ni España ni otros 12 países han firmado un "acuerdo climático global" para abolir la agricultura
108	Medio grado más de calor es imperceptible para los humanos, pero el planeta sí nota sus consecuencias
109	Biden no ha negado que el cambio climático sea un problema
110	Qué es y para qué sirve el secuestro de carbono
111	El Parlamento Europeo no ha aceptado la solicitud de Ucrania para entrar en la UE
112	Si has visto a Greta Thunberg desnuda en un vídeo es un "deepfake"
113	Vídeo prova que BP tem "esquema" para cobrar un litro a mais de combustível do que o realmente abastecido?
114	No, esta foto del festival de Glastonbury (Inglaterra) repleto de basura no fue tomada tras el reciente discurso de Greta Thunberg: es de 2015
115	Qué es la Agenda 2030 y qué dicen los bulos virales que desinforman sobre este plan impulsado por la ONU
116	Los otros cambios climáticos
117	El bulo de que la Unión Europea pide a la población que descarte el desayuno para preservar el medioambiente
118	Produção de bateria para carro elétrico polui mais do que um carro a combustão em 20 anos?
119	Este anuncio no anima a los alemanes a no tener hijos por su impacto en el clima, es el cartel de un reportaje de 2020
120	Quién está detrás del documento viral que señala que "no existe la emergencia climática"
121	La UE no ha anunciado que vaya a limitar el consumo de prendas de ropa a tres por persona al año por la Agenda 2030
122	No es cierto que el actual cambio climático tenga precedentes históricos, como dice Ayuso
123	Los modelos no han predicho que Groenlandia se quedaría sin hielo en 2022
124	Estas imagens da Terra foram captadas por missão espacial indiana a partir da Lua?
125	La NASA no ha admitido que el cambio climático se debe a la órbita terrestre
126	No es cierto que "hagas lo que hagas, no vas a cambiar nada" respecto al cambio climático, tal y como indica el youtuber Dalas
127	La Comisión Europea no planeó antes de la pandemia aprobar el pasaporte covid
128	Bill Gates no ha admitido en este vídeo que la vacunación fue un "terrible error"
129	Vacinas contra a Covid-19 "podem ser a forma de combater as crises climáticas", revela-se nas redes sociais
130	Los niveles de CO2 actuales son los más altos de la historia de la humanidad, pero no del planeta

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N	Hoax
131	Los huracanes no son creados artificialmente por el ser humano
132	No, Greta Thunberg no ha pedido usar "misiles biodegradables" ni "granadas veganas": el vídeo está manipulado
133	No, Greta Thunberg no tuiteó en 2018 que "el fin de la humanidad por el cambio climático" llegaría en 2023: habló de "los próximos cinco años" como margen de acción
134	Governo da Alemanha financiou fundação de Bill Gates em 3,8 mil milhões de euros para garantir "controlo populacional"?
135	Bill Gates é neto do co-fundador da fundação Rockefeller, Frederik Taylor Gates?
136	Las renovables tienen una huella de carbono decenas de veces menor que las fósiles pese al impacto inicial de su construcción
137	Greta Thunberg no ha escrito un libro llamado "Vegan wars" en el que pide fabricar tanques sostenibles
138	Diz-se no Facebook: "Granelândia não é afetada pelo aquecimento global provocado pelo homem"
139	ONU promove "a fome mundial" para "implementar 'A Grande Reinicialização'", descobre-se nas redes sociais
140	Desmatamento da Amazônia baixou 48% na Presidência de Jair Bolsonaro em comparação com Lula da Silva
141	La noticia de que en Sevilla se registraron 51 °C en 1876 no prueba que el cambio climático no exista
142	La historia de Bill Gates y el vendedor de periódicos "más rico del mundo": un bulo que se mueve internacionalmente
143	Glosario de terminología climática
144	Que España tenga más superficie forestal arbolada que hace 100 años no significa que los ecosistemas estén más sanos
145	Que haya cambio climático en otros planetas no significa que el de la Tierra lo esté causando el Sol
146	Es falso que no exista una «crisis climática real», como asegura el Nobel John Clauser
147	El hielo del Ártico no se expande ni ha alcanzado su nivel máximo en 30 años
148	Grupo de ativistas climáticos está a esvaziar pneus de carros SUV em Portugal. Configura um crime?
149	Não, onda de calor em 1949 não prova que o aquecimento global é uma invenção
150	Elon Musk banii Greta Thunberg do Twitter?
151	Qué dice y qué no dice el estudio sobre el aumento de hielo en zonas de la Antártida y por qué no significa que la crisis climática no sea real
152	La UE no ha pedido descartar el desayuno para preservar el medioambiente
153	Cambio climático no es lo mismo que calentamiento global
154	El aumento de hielo marino en la Antártida no es una prueba válida para negar el calentamiento global
155	Las nubes sí afectan al clima, pero no han causado el cambio climático actual
156	El vídeo de las inundaciones en Madrid en 1966 no desmiente el cambio climático
157	Es falso que los récords recientes de temperatura se batieron porque la ESA "ahora mide la temperatura de la superficie y no la del aire"

These hoaxes will later be analyzed in the following sections. Furthermore, we found these channels affected by the hoaxes. There are many more channels affected by the analysis, reflecting the widespread width of climate disinformation. In this regard, we found international reach for these hoaxes (Table 4).

Table 4. Climate change channels.

N	Channel	N	Channel	N	Channel
1	ActiveClubXIV	62	FREEDOMFIGHTERSWW	122	realx22report
2	agentsoftruth	63	gatewaypunditofficial	123	redicetv
3	akademidergisii	64	GeneralMCNews	124	redlistupdatesuk
4	AltSkull48	65	GenWarz	125	RedPillDealer4833
5	AntiVac	66	geoingenierieinfo	126	RevealedEye
6	anto_boyle_channel	67	gintaras_fpublic	127	sapereaudelt
7	artwithaim	68	greatreject	128	shadowman2020
8	asprievakcinacija	69	gregoryroose	129	SicilianGorillian2
9	atsbudimas	70	GutmenschenKeule	130	sntx_cosmic
10	AusraBiguzaite11	71	haberinizolsungangalargrubu	131	soberaniajusticiasocial
11	ayyildizhabertr	72	haberw	132	son_dakika_haberr
12	bagelsandshadeshow	73	hiddeninplainsight1	133	son_dakika1
13	BBCisTheVIRUS	74	hispanospatriotas	134	sotten
14	BrainlessChanel	75	insider_amigo	135	STFNREPORT
15	BritainFirst	76	insiderpaper	136	stopconfinamiento
16	BritishNursingAllianceSpeak	77	intelslava	137	stopmanipulacionclimatica
17	CACUKsupport	78	intheboxWithJohnLawrence	138	SunflowerSociety
18	cadizcontraelpasaportecovid	79	jordansather	139	supercontagadores
19	canalcristianosporlaverdad	80	JotvingisLietuvis	140	surf_noise_eng
20	candlesinthenight	81	JustDudeChannel	141	TakeOurCountryBack
21	CaptKylePatriots	82	KanekoaTheGreat	142	the_Right_People
22	CHDEurope	83	LA_BITACORA	143	The_Storm_Q17
23	chemtrailsaquintacolumna	84	LARECONQUISTA_ESP	144	TheBigConspiracy
24	chiefnerd	85	LauraAbolichannel	145	TheConspiracyHole
25	childcovidvaccineinjuriesuk	86	laverdadlibre	146	TheEndOfEverything1
26	CIG_telegram	87	marioamenti	147	thegoldenone
27	concienciagalactica	88	MartinCostelloNews	148	TheGreatResetTimes

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N	Channel	N	Channel	N	Channel
28	conscienciaterraplana	89	medicosporlaverdadar	149	TheLightTruthPaper
29	coronapsyopscam	90	meghUpdates	150	ThePatriotAU
30	CoronavirusPlushie	91	mincevicius	151	thepeopleslawyerchannel
31	covid19vaccinevictims	92	MurderTheMedia	152	theresistanceengland
32	COVID19VACCINEVICTIMSANDFAMILIES	93	nastikatube	153	theriotimes
33	CovidCrimestoppers	94	naujoji_pasaulio_tvarka	154	TheSovereignSoul
34	covidland_espanol	95	neadeqatus	155	TheTruthFairy
35	craigkelly	96	negacionistasmx	156	TommyRobinsonNews
36	darkuniverse09	97	neofeminismo	157	totaldisclosure
37	davidickeofficial	98	No_BS_News	158	trabajadoresportalibertad
38	despiertaUruguay	99	noalavacuna	159	Triada_oscura
39	dokuz8haber	100	node_of_time_en	160	trumpintel
40	dotconnectinganons	101	Not_On_The_Beeb	161	truthwins888
41	Dr_Angel_Ruiz_Valdepe_as	102	nuevahumanidadhuelva	162	UKcitizen2021
42	Dr_DavidMartinWorld	103	OPERAC_ENJAMBRE	163	ultrasnotreds2
43	dr_judymikovitss	104	PADRESPORLAVERDAD	164	UncleSamsNYPBs
44	DrMikeYeadon	105	paremosNewOrdenMundial	165	unitednationalistfront
45	DrPaulMarik	106	PatriotVoiceOfficial	166	uyan2021
46	DrTenpenny	107	PLANDEMIA_MUNDIAL_COVID	167	Uyanis_Turkiye
47	eduardomenoni1	108	PlantBasedNews	168	Vaccinelnjuriesca
48	ejercitoremnante	109	police_frequency	169	vacunaspeligrosas
49	elaullido	110	PrivateCanadianNews	170	vakcinudiskusijos
50	EiContrafuerte	111	professor_patriot_official	171	varlinas
51	EiDiestro	112	protest	172	vaziyetcomtr
52	elinvestigador_org	113	ptpatriots	173	victoriaenlaluz
53	ellocodelacorralachannel	114	publicannouncement602967921	174	VigilantFox
54	elpuebloxlaverdad	115	QAnon17_Awakening	175	WeaponizeConspiracy
55	euskalnews	116	qanonplus	176	wolfchannel2
56	ExponiendoLaElite	117	QlobalChangeUSA	177	worlddoctorsalliance
57	exponiendolaverdadoculta	118	QNewsOfficialTV	178	worldwidewakeup
58	Fall_of_the_Cabal	119	rafapalreal	179	zeeemedia
59	FionaRoseDiamond	120	realDonaldjTrump	180	zoomerwaffen08
60	flayfm	121	RealRebelNews	181	ZoroKanalas
61	ForoPXLVE				

With triple the hoaxes and several more channels for research, this section becomes more challenging to analyse. It stands to reason that Climate change, which has been a long-standing topic of interest for disinformation spreaders, to have this extended interest in terms of volume and width.

There are still some errors in the retrieval algorithm. Take hoax 1 for example, talking about malaria. Other hoaxes are tangentially related to climate change, for example hoax 112 discussing photos on Greta Thunberg, a prominent climate change activist; however, despite the personality being an activist there's no claim made about climate itself. Hoax 134 for instance, talks about population control, which is a popular proxy topic for talking about climate change as a conspiracy, however the hoax itself makes no assertions about climate either.

Many climate change hoaxes aren't specifically mentioning "climate change" or "global warming", instead they focus on normalizing extraordinary climate events. Take for instance hoax 38, which tries to normalize the Greenland defrosting. However, these are scarce, most of the misinformation targets policy and political entities; these can be easily found across the entire list, attacking institutions like the European Union, NASA and other well-respected entities. This is shared between hoaxes on

climate change and Covid-19; many of these conspiracy theories are disproportionately attacking established institutions, muddling their reputation through questionable claims.

Scientific well-reported facts are dismissed as false, such as defrosting, CO2 emissions and so on. As well as institutional attacks, this seems to be a recurrent theme across topics, so it begs the question: which motivates the other? Do misinformation actors distrust institutions because they disbelieve scientific facts? Or is it the other way around? We find these questions interesting, but find it difficult to respond.

More observations are repeated from Covid-19 channels, however this time they extend internationally. Patriotic channels, fake media outlets, skeptic communities. Some repeat appearances are 'rafapalreal' or 'ejercitoremamente', which points toward that misinformation actors are transversal, following several conspiracies simultaneously. This last assertion tracks out, because some affected channels are 'noalavacuna' or 'supercontagadores'. The channel selection is also composed of several far-right figureheads such as 'thegoldenone' or 'qanonplus'; as well as reactionary dogwhistles such as 'RedPillDealer4833' with the red pill manosphere analogy, or 'truthwins888' with the use of 88 which is shorthand for HH or Heil Hitler.

As before, visualizations have been extracted from all hoaxes, with three of them hand-picked for examination. Hoaxes 18, 43 and 74 illustrate some patterns worth examining. In Section 3, they are commented in detail.

2.3 Gender issues hoaxes and actors

We present the hoaxes found for LGBTIQ+ and gender issues in Table 5.

Table 5. Gender issues Hoaxes. In spanish & portuguese

N	Hoax
1	¿Qué sabemos de este vídeo en el que la policía alemana separa a dos niños de sus padres por supuestamente "no aceptar la doctrina LGBTI"?
2	¿Qué sabemos de esta imagen de dos mujeres trans "robando" el primer y segundo puesto de una carrera de ciclismo femenina?
3	El bulo de que el PP retiró la bandera LGBTI del ayuntamiento de Valencia el 17 de junio de 2023
4	Greta Thunberg no hizo un llamado a tener guerras más sostenibles, es un «deepfake»
5	Disney no se arrepiente de apoyar ideas LGBTI porque le haga perder dinero
6	El cartel que pide excluir a «las mujeres biológicas» del 8M no es de una convocatoria verídica
7	El papa no ha legalizado las bodas homosexuales
8	El bulo que asegura que Kristian Nairn, actor de 'Juego de Tronos', ha mostrado su "transición a mujer"
9	Vox y PP no han "prohibido" utilizar banderas LGBTI en espacios públicos en Nàquera, el acuerdo se refiere a los edificios municipales
10	El Partido Popular no retiró la bandera LGBTI del Ayuntamiento de Valencia el 17 de junio, fue el anterior Gobierno
11	El cuerpo no es un reloj y la mayoría de las mujeres no tiene la regla cada veintiocho días
12	Cuando los bulos se convierten en un "arma para la deshumanización" de las personas trans
13	¿Qué sabemos de la luchadora que derrota a otras mujeres en este vídeo, a quien acusan de ser trans?
14	No es una agresión a una chica trans por inmigrantes en España
15	Cuidado con los vídeos de hombres que dicen haber hecho el cambio de sexo registral "de un día para otro" para "beneficiarse" de la ley trans
16	No, la foto de esta niña no es de Ucrania: es una refugiada afgana fotografiada en Pakistán en 2014
17	Una trans asesina a tres prostitutas hace más de 30 años en Estados Unidos: por qué no decir dónde y cuándo ha ocurrido un suceso puede generar desinformación
18	Ministério da Defesa trocou bandeira nacional por bandeira LGBTQIA+?
19	Assédio sexual na Universidade de Coimbra. Denúncia "sem nomes" é válida em processo legal?
20	Exército do Brasil vai criar "unidade especial de batalhão LGBT"?
21	No, el PP no ha presentado un recurso de inconstitucionalidad contra la 'ley trans' el Día del Orgullo LGBTI: ese día se ha publicado en el BOE su admisión a trámite
22	El bulo de que el presupuesto de más de 20.000 millones de euros del plan estratégico de Igualdad se destinará a "charlas feministas"
23	La joven trans víctima de agresión sexual en Valladolid recibió asistencia legal por ser menor y no por "declararse mujer"
24	Miss Colômbia disse em concurso que "homens" não deviam concorrer contra "mulheres verdadeiras"?

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N	Hoax
25	Este combate no es entre "un gigante hombre trans" y "una joven chica", son dos luchadoras de jiu-jitsu
26	El bulo de que Gabi Garcia es trans y ha matado a la luchadora Bárbara Nepomuceno en combate
27	Sede da ONU trocou as 193 bandeiras nacionais por bandeiras arco-íris do "orgulho 'gay'"?
28	Las desinformaciones sobre el acuerdo entre Vox y PP, las banderas LGTBI y las concentraciones contra la violencia machista en Náquera (Valencia)
29	La imagen de un hombre en un desfile del Orgullo vistiendo una camiseta con el mensaje "los niños trans son sexy" es falsa
30	É proibido erguer bandeiras LGBTQIA+ durante as cerimónias da JMJ?
31	Abortar no provoca más problemas de salud mental que no hacerlo
32	Imagem mostra sala de aulas em Portugal com a bandeira LGBT e do movimento "Black Lives Matter"?
33	El bulo tráfobo que se repite país a país: Michelle Obama, Brigitte Macron y, ahora, Beqoña Gómez
34	No, el Ministerio de Igualdad no ha "encargado" una campaña contra la violencia de género en la que aparece la reina Letizia como una "mujer maltratada"
35	Greta Thunberg no obligó a unos manifestantes a dejar de respirar por el clima
36	El Tribunal Europeo de Derechos Humanos no anuló el matrimonio homosexual
37	Quando era homem não ganhava nada, diz Ventura sobre atleta trans que venceu oito troféus no feminino. É verdade?
38	Bulos de la campaña para el 19J en Andalucía
39	No son falsas víctimas ucranianas sino manifestantes contra el cambio climático
40	No, no es cierto que se haya censurado el beso LGTBI de la película 'Lightyear' en Cines Yelmo
41	Disney vai abrir rede de clínicas pediátricas para crianças transgênero?
42	No es un supuesto activista LGTBI «indignado», sino un humorista en un vídeo parodia
43	Este vídeo de una madre que arranca una bandera LGTBIQ+ de una clase es una recreación "humorística" con actores
44	No, Público no ha publicado un artículo titulado "sexo empoderante" sobre una campaña del Ministerio de Igualdad sobre "las otras penetraciones"
45	La bandera que lleva el alumnado en este colegio de Argentina no es la del colectivo LGTBI, sino la del cooperativismo
46	Las cifras sobre los delitos sexuales no reflejan necesariamente su evolución real: se denuncian menos y más tarde que el resto
47	No es un montaje de Photoshop: Cepsa sí ha puesto la bandera LGTBI en sus gasolineras
48	¿Qué sabemos sobre si el tirador de Illinois es una mujer trans? Las autoridades afirman que usó ropa de mujer para huir
49	No, los detenidos por agredir a una pareja homosexual en Elche (Alicante) no son "menas magrebies"
50	Las cifras sobre los delitos sexuales no reflejan necesariamente su evolución real: se denuncian menos y más tarde que el resto
51	Italia no ha eliminado el tercer género de los DNI: nunca ha existido esta opción
52	La Generalitat no pidió a las mujeres que prueben a usar el velo islámico
53	Greta Thunberg no ha pedido que se usen las centrales nucleares
54	No, este supuesto sorteo de una tarjeta regalo de 750€ por el Día Internacional de la Mujer no es de Shein
55	Las preguntas que nunca te has atrevido a hacer sobre sexo
56	¿Puede perder sus derechos el colectivo LGTBI en Madrid?
57	El papa Francisco no porta en estas imágenes una cruz con los colores de la bandera LGTBI
58	Los fondos europeos en materia de violencia de género no se reparten en función del número de denuncias de cada país
59	No, Público no ha publicado un artículo titulado "sexo empoderante" sobre una campaña del Ministerio de Igualdad sobre "las otras penetraciones"
60	No, el hombre de esta foto no lleva una camiseta durante un desfile del Orgullo LGTBI en la que pone que "los niños trans son sexys": la imagen está manipulada
61	La desinformación que vincula un supuesto embarazo en el módulo de mujeres de una prisión de Alicante con la ley trans
62	España cayó de posición en un ranking internacional de bienestar de la mujer aunque mejoró su puntuación
63	Desinformaciones sobre la foto de una mujer embarazada en la explosión de un hospital infantil de Mariupol (Ucrania)
64	Escola de Medicina de Harvard promove curso para pediatras identificarem "bebés LGBTQIA+?"
65	Esta foto muestra una manifestación de ciclistas, no una marcha del Orgullo
66	El Gobierno español no considera discapacitadas a todas las víctimas de violencia de género
67	Es falso que en España sea legal cambiarse de género cada 6 meses
68	No, la ley trans no establece "un subsidio para personas trans mayores de 65 años": se trata de una propuesta rechazada y estaba destinada a quienes "no superen la renta mínima"
69	Quem levantar a bandeira LGBT no Mundial de Futebol [do Qatar] vai ficar preso por 7 a 11 anos, alerta-se nas redes sociais
70	Druni no está promocionando una tarjeta regalo de 800 euros por el Día Internacional de la Mujer, es una estafa
71	La bandera LGTBI no incorporó los colores de Ucrania en señal de apoyo frente a Rusia
72	No, ningún "portavoz del Mundial de Catar" ha declarado que enseñar la bandera LGTBI estará penado con "entre siete y once años de cárcel" a 29 de junio de 2022"
73	La historia de la niña que aparece rescatada por tres personas diferentes: pasaba de unos brazos a otros tras un bombardeo en Siria
74	La "boda LGTBIQ+" entre una mujer militar y otra activista en Ucrania no es real, se trata de una acción reivindicativa
75	La ONU no ha publicado un informe que pide legalizar la pederastia y la Agenda 2030 tampoco la promueve
76	Lido no Facebook: "Governo obriga polícias e câmaras municipais a hastear a bandeira LGBT"
77	Preguntas y respuestas sobre la fusión de los delitos de agresión y abuso sexual en la ley del 'solo sí es sí' y su relación con el Convenio de Estambul
78	Cuidado con la cuenta trol @TrinidadNovo que se hace pasar por "feminista, socialdemócrata y animalista"
79	Escocia, Alemania y Australia no están revirtiendo sus leyes trans, pese a lo que afirma Borja Sémper
80	Es falso que en Alemania una familia perdiera la custodia de sus hijos por estar en contra del colectivo LGTBI
81	El vídeo viral de una agresión a una chica trans es antiguo y se grabó en Bélgica
82	De "binário" a "homem trans" ou "queer". Registo de género nas Conservatórias em Portugal inclui 20 opções?
83	Los bulos virales en torno a las protestas por la reforma de las pensiones en Francia
84	Estacionamiento prioritario para casais LGBT será obrigatório até 2024?
85	Nos preguntáis si Biden violó el Código de la Bandera de EEUU al colocar el emblema LGTBI en la Casa Blanca
86	Este vídeo del Arco del Triunfo de París decorado con un arcoiris gigante por el mes del Orgullo es una recreación digital
87	La bailarina Sophie Rebecca no ha sido contratada por la Royal Academy of Dance o admitida por ser mujer trans
88	Glenique Frank, mujer trans, no ganó la maratón de Londres: quedó en el puesto 6.182 de la competición no profesional
89	La ley de solo sí es sí no exigirá un contrato de consentimiento sexual
90	La ley trans y los términos 'madre' y 'padre': no se eliminan ni cambian por 'progenitor gestante' o 'no gestante' del Código Civil sino que conviven
91	La modelo Bella Hadid no ha mostrado su apoyo a Israel en este vídeo
92	¿Qué sabemos sobre la campaña 'El verano también es nuestro' del Ministerio de Igualdad?
93	ONU disse que cristãos que não aceitem legalização da pedofilia vão ser "expulsos da sociedade"?

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N	Hoax
94	Campeonato Mundial de Fútbol Femenino marcado por "estádios vacíos"?
95	Não vou competir contra um homem. Miss EUA boicota concurso Miss Universo por causa de concorrente "trans"?
96	El cambio de sexo registral no permite eludir una condena por violencia de género
97	Las desinformaciones sobre las indemnizaciones por cese a los altos cargos del Ministerio de Igualdad
98	No, esta foto de dos niños paseando entre hombres desnudos no es de la celebración del Orgullo LGTB de 2023 en Madrid: está tomada en Londres y se difunde desde al menos 2022
99	Cuidado con el perfil de Twitter Valentivalente que ha tuiteado que "poco se habla de los derechos trans de los fetos": es una cuenta trol
100	Netflix no ha eliminado una serie de dibujos animados con contenido LGTB en la que uno de sus personajes es de género no binario
101	No, esta imagen no muestra a "un tío que, gracias a la nueva ley trans, puede sentirse mujer y jugar en la liga femenina", al contrario: es un hombre trans que no puede jugar en un equipo masculino porque aún no se le reconoce como hombre
102	La inhibición de la fertilidad no es un efecto secundario de la vacunación
103	El Ministerio de Igualdad no organizó un "Día de la Diversidad de las Vaginas"
104	Los artículos que alertan de que más del 82% de las embarazadas vacunadas sufrirán abortos se basan en un estudio erróneo
105	Dois atletas trans venceram corrida de bicicletas exclusivamente para mulheres?
106	Los bulos sobre series y contenidos inclusivos en las plataformas de 'streaming'
107	Rezar frente a una clínica abortiva no está prohibido, como afirma Catalán (UPN), pero puede ser delito si deriva en acoso
108	Si has visto a Greta Thunberg desnuda en un vídeo es un "deepfake"
109	Novedades sobre la menstruación y la vacuna de la covid 19
110	No, esta foto no muestra cómo "han quedado las calles de Madrid" después de "las fiestas del Orgullo" LGTB de 2022: la imagen circula desde, al menos, 2019
111	¿Qué sabemos sobre la supuesta "abogada transgénero canadiense que alega discriminación porque un ginecólogo rechazó tratarla al tener genitales masculinos"?
112	Orgullo LGBTQ+: los bulos que desinforman en redes sociales sobre las personas del colectivo en 2023
113	La ONU no ha pedido despenalizar la pedofilia, es un informe tergiversado
114	Italia no incluye el género no binario en su carné de identidad
115	La UE no sancionará al Real Madrid por negarse a apoyar a la comunidad LGTB
116	No existen registros de la 'Asociación Transgénero Anti-Ciencia': el cartel viral procede de una cuenta parodia
117	La niña ensangrentada no fue herida en Ucrania, sino en Siria hace 4 años
118	El detenido por agresión sexual a una reportera no es su novio
119	Catar no impondrá penas de cárcel por mostrar la bandera LGTB en el Mundial de fútbol
120	Nos preguntáis si unas «bomberas feministas» incendiaron accidentalmente un parque en Canadá
121	No hay registros de que Giorgia Meloni haya declarado el mes del "Orgullo Familiar" para contrarrestar el Orgullo LGTB en Italia
122	El vídeo de una mujer arrancando una bandera LGTB de un aula es ficticio
123	Cuidado con el perfil de Jennytrans17 que asegura que las trans son "las verdaderas mujeres": es una cuenta trol
124	¿Qué sabemos sobre el cartel supuestamente del Banco Santander con motivo del 8-M, Día Internacional de la Mujer? Desde la entidad afirman que no es suyo
125	No, este sorteo de Druni por el Día de la Mujer no es real: es un timo
126	No hay fotos que prueben que el asesino de Texas era trans
127	Lidl niega que vaya a despedir a una empleada de su supermercado por llamar 'caballero' a una mujer trans en repetidas ocasiones
128	Dato mata relato: un recopilatorio para combatir las principales desinformaciones sobre feminismo de 2023
129	El bulo del estreno en España de la película 'Corpus Christi' que "muestra a Jesús y a sus discípulos como homosexuales"
130	Soria no gastó 20.000 euros en un taller feminista ni lo pagó el plan de Igualdad
131	No, este supuesto sorteo de un brazalete por el Día Internacional de la Mujer no es de Pandora
132	Miguel Esteves Cardoso escreveu frase homofóbica contra "manifestação do orgulho gay"?
133	El Foro Económico Mundial no ha pedido despenalizar la pedofilia
134	Orange no patrocinaba la lona de Vox que "tira a la basura" la bandera LGBTQ+ o el logo feminista
135	ONU recomienda que "as crianças devem ter parceiros sexuais"?
136	Este vídeo no demuestra que en Alemania separan a hijos de sus familias por estar en contra del colectivo LGTB
137	No, este vídeo de varias personas teniendo sexo en la calle ni es del Orgullo ni fue grabado en Madrid: es de un festival sobre prácticas eróticas en Estados Unidos
138	¿Qué sabemos sobre las denuncias de los pinchazos en discotecas?****
139	Catar no organiza ejecuciones públicas a homosexuales
140	El Ministerio de Igualdad no ha lanzado una campaña a favor del "sexo empoderante" para "visibilizar otras penetraciones", es un montaje
141	La sede de la ONU no ha cambiado las banderas de los países miembro por las del Orgullo LGTB, es la plaza de Rockefeller Center
142	¿Qué sabemos sobre la supuesta quedada del colectivo gay "Sevilla no se calla" del próximo sábado en la puerta del Ayuntamiento, para piropear" a la Virgen de las Mercedes?
143	André Ventura sugere que movimentos LGBT "querem descriminalizar o sexo entre pessoas e animais"
144	Bulos que usan fotos de personas trans para acusarles de ser el autor del tiroteo de Texas (EEUU)
145	El Ayuntamiento de Granada no ha anunciado una ordenanza contra el colectivo LGTB para sancionar sus atuendos
146	¿Qué sabemos del caso de "transfobia" que se produjo en un establecimiento de Lidl en Málaga y de que la empresa vaya a despedir a una trabajadora que se vio implicada?
147	Escola de inglês em Almada só dá aulas a homossexuais?
148	La Generalitat aporta fondos al Alto Comisionado de Derechos Humanos de la ONU, pero el Gobierno central y el vasco también
149	No, una mujer transgénero no ha ganado la maratón de Londres 2023

We analyze these hoaxes in detail in the following sections. Associated with these hoaxes, we present the channels in Table 6. As with climate change, we found many more channels with international reach.

Table 6. Gender issues Channels.

N	Channel	N	Channel	N	Channel
1	AFLDSOrg	74	SETexasProudBoys	146	insider_amigo
2	ActiveClubXIV	75	STFNREPORT	147	insiderpaper

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N	Channel	N	Channel	N	Channel
3	AltSkull48	76	SicilianGorillian2	148	joinmiFight
4	AntiVac	77	SunflowerSociety	149	jordansather
5	AntiVaxAus	78	TakeOurCountryBack	150	marioamenti
6	Anti Feminist Gang	79	TheBigConspiracy	151	markacollett
7	Antivaxxforms	80	TheConspiracyHole	152	mediaandcensoring
8	AwakenedOutlaw	81	TheEndOfEverything1	153	medicosporlaverdadar
9	BBCisTheVIRUS	82	TheGreatResetTimes	154	meghUpdates
10	BLUEPRINT_Q	83	TheLightTruthPaper	155	mha haber
11	BrainlessChanel	84	ThePatriotAU	156	mincevicus
12	BritainFirst	85	TheSovereignSoul	157	mindcontrolmonarchmkultra
13	BritishNursingAllianceSpeak	86	TheTruthFairy	158	monitoestepario
14	CHDEurope	87	The Storm_Q17	159	mpeinovich
15	CIG telegram	88	The Zionist Effect	160	nastikatube
16	COVID19VACCINEVICTIMSAND FAMILIES	89	TommyRobinsonNews	161	naujoji pasaulio tvarka
17	CaptKylePatriots	90	Triada oscura	162	neadeqatus
18	CovidCrimestoppers	91	TruthHammer	163	negacionistasmx
19	Daily Clout	92	TruthIsStillHateSpeech	164	neofeminismo
20	DrJaneRuby	93	UKcitizen2021	165	neolduhaber
21	DrMikeYeadon	94	UncleSamsNYPBs	166	node_of_time_en
22	DrPaulAlexander	95	Uyanis Turkiye	167	nuevahumanidadhuelva
23	DrPaulMarik	96	VaccineInjuriesca	168	oldworld42
24	DrSimoneGold	97	VigilantFox	169	orlaredchan
25	DrTenpenny	98	WeaponizeConspiracy	170	paremosNewOrdenMundial
26	Dr_DavidMartinWorld	99	ZmogusAntanasZemaitis	171	police_frequency
27	EIDiestro	100	ZoroKanalas	172	professor_patriot_official
28	ExponiendoLaElite	101	afldsc	173	protest
29	FREEDOMFIGHTERSWW	102	agentsoftruth	174	ptkRelm
30	FaithAndFolk2	103	akademidergisii	175	ptpatriots
31	Fall of the Cabal	104	akincilarkarargahi	176	publicannouncement602967921
32	ForoPXLVE	105	ancreport	177	qanonplus
33	GenWarz	106	anto_boyle_channel	178	r_turkey
34	GeneralMCNews	107	artwithaim	179	rafapalreal
35	GoodLionNews	108	asprievaksinacija	180	realDonaldjTrump
36	GutmenschenKeule	109	awakenedworlduk	181	realx22report
37	HarveyRisch	110	bagelsandshadeshow	182	redicetv
38	InformationEqualsDecisions	111	cadizcontraelpasaportecovid	183	returnofthesacred
39	IntheboxWithJohnLawrence	112	canal antifeminista	184	risingrxce
40	JotvingisLietuvis	113	canalcristianosporlaverdad	185	rothschildbankingfamily
41	JustDudeChannel	114	candlesinthenight	186	saintsandscholars
42	KanekoaTheGreat	115	chiefnerd	187	sancakgundem
43	LARECONQUISTA_ESP	116	childcovidvaccineinjuriesuk	188	sapereaudelt
44	LA_BITACORA	117	cienciaycovid	189	sntx cosmic
45	LauraAbolichannel	118	concienciagalactica	190	son_dakika_haberr
46	MartinCostelloNews	119	conscienciaterraplana	191	sotten
47	MissFreedomSeeker	120	coronapsyopscam	192	supercontagiadores
48	MurderTheMedia	121	covid19vaccinevictims	193	surf_noise_eng
49	NemesisParis	122	covidland espanol	194	the Right People
50	No BS News	123	craigkelly	195	thegoldenone
51	Not On The Beeb	124	darkuniverse09	196	thepeopleslawyerchannel
52	OPERAC ENJAMBRE	125	davidickeofficial	197	theresistanceengland
53	OdeToPower2	126	despiertaUruguay	198	theriotimes
54	OfficialRedPillNews	127	dokuz8haber	199	totaldisclosure
55	PADRESPORLAVERDAD	128	dotconnectinganons	200	toyotadshk
56	PLANDEMIA_MUNDIAL_COVID	129	eduardomenoni1	201	trumpintel
57	PatAltNorthWest	130	ejercitoremante	202	truthwins888
58	PatAltScotland	131	ellocodelacorralachannel	203	ultrasnotreds2
59	PatriotVoiceOfficial	132	euskalnews	204	unitednationalistfront
60	PatrioticAlternativeOfficial	133	familiasporlaverdadcolombia	205	vacunaspeligrosas
61	PlantBasedNews	134	flayfm	206	vakcinudiskusijos
62	Pornuestrosninos	135	gatewaypunditofficial	207	varlinas
63	PrivateCanadianNews	136	generationidentitaire	208	vaziyetcomtr
64	QAnon17_Awakening	137	greatreject	209	virtudnacional
65	QNewsOfficialTV	138	griffincomtr	210	whitelaborstrikkeww
66	QlobalChangeUSA	139	haberalert	211	wolfchannel2
67	Qnews	140	haberbiz	212	worlddoctorsalliance
68	RadioGenoa	141	haberinvarmi TR	213	worldwidewakeup
69	RealDonaldTrumpo	142	habermedya	214	yaylahaber

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N	Channel	N	Channel	N	Channel
70	RealRebelNews	143	hiddeninplainsight1	215	zaferpartililer
71	RedPillDealer4833	144	brahimhaskologlu	216	zeeemedia
72	RevealedEye	145	infoburbuja	217	zoomerwaffen08
73	RogerHodkinson				

Unlike previous hoax tables, the gender-related hoaxes have been mostly correctly identified with fewer errors than usual. There are some outliers like Greta Thunberg disinformation again, but this could be traced to sexism too. Some hoaxes, at first glance, seem unrelated; however this is far from the truth, take for instance hoax 75 where pedophilia is mentioned. Pedophilia and LGBTIQ+ are separate topics but within far-right rhetoric, queer identities are usually falsely associated with attraction to minors, which is a common hoax divulged in far-right circles. So, in the end it seems that hoaxes found remain mostly on-topic.

This comes at a cost. Gender-related misinformation is a huge scope, bigger than climate change even, as it includes transphobia, sexism, homophobia and so on. The result is a mixed bag of hoaxes touching every sub-topic about these issues. We'll delve first into transphobia, which is one of the most prevalent sub-topics. A lot of transphobic disinformation comes from sport competitions, overall gender reassignment legislation and panic over children. There's plenty of hoaxes relating to LGTB symbols, like flags (and their legislation) and their inclusion in everyday lives, as well as LGTB pride day. Other hoaxes signal to sexism, especially attacking the "Women's day" and feminism movements. There's very little direct homophobia, usually present by proxy in hatred towards LGBT symbols/movement.

Finally we observe the channels discovered along these hoaxes. The volume of channels is larger than before, despite the same number of hoaxes. Aside from the increased volume of channels, we observe similar traits in the collection as with climate change disinformation and Covid-19. There's a lot of overlap with Anti-vaxx movements.

We chose three hoaxes from the list to analyse in full, these being hoax number 19, 47 and 89. They are considered interesting, with illustrative trends.

3. Visualization assessment

From the chosen hoaxes, we have selected a few to be visualized, as well as the overall dynamics of dissemination. Each topic has its separate analysis, with a final analysis of common trends. Some comments about cascade visualizations.

- Visualizations contain only the channels detected by the algorithm. We seed messages across all channels mentioned in the previous section, but only a few may appear. Not all channels talk about the same hoaxes and this is reflected in cascades.
- Arrows indicate link strength. The more opaque, the strongest the chance of them being linked together. Usually, when completely black, it represents a copy-paste, repost or similar interaction. Some interactions are so weak that have been removed from the graph, despite not shown, they are still a tree.
- Dot size represents the amount of views in log scale, larger dots are vastly more influential.
- Color is randomized to distinguish between channels.

3.1 Covid-19 cascades and influence

We begin our analysis on Hoax 4: “[Translated] Beware of the video about the Queen Elizabeth II COVID-19 positive that included an image of ivermectin: there is no evidence of what she is ingesting and the emission’s network assured it was an error.”. This alludes to “Queen Elizabeth II is taking ivermectin to counter COVID-19.”. Figure 1 shows the cascade for this hoax.

Figure 1. Hoax 4 Covid-19: Cuidado con el vídeo sobre el positivo en Covid-19 de la reina Isabel II que incluye una imagen de la ivermectina: no hay pruebas de que lo esté tomando y la cadena que lo emitió asegura que fue un error

Five channels have been found to have interest in this hoax. First, we observe a large influential wave of messages from the “PADRESPORLAVERDAD” channel; they published a large amount before mostly dropping the topic after June’22. However, they began a widespread campaign across rafapalreal, medicosporlaverdadESP and so on, where their messages show to have very strong relations to outer channels.

Their publishing ignited discussion frequently in rafapalreal, which is another massively influential channel that kept the topic going until around June’22. In this intermediate period, links and messages are rarer, but still very prevalent. Interestingly, most

messages seem to be influenced by “PADRESPORLAVERDAD” despite the temporal drop-off implanted into our algorithm, this seems to indicate a very strong connection between the earliest forms of discussion and the later stages of discourse. Furthermore, despite their repeated discourse about the topic, “rafapalreal” rarely influences other channels. This is untrue for the other satellite channels like “elinvestigador_org” where information is crossposted across other channels and influences others.

In this graph, we deem “PADRESPORLAVERDAD” overwhelmingly influential. They sparked the topic’s discussion among the chosen channels, and set in stone the main directions of discussion through the entire lifecycle of the hoax.

Our analysis continues on Hoax 9: “[Translated] *It is false that the COVID-19 vaccine has produced ‘tens of thousands deaths’ as a magazine confirms*”. This alludes to “*Covid-19 vaccine has caused more than ten thousand deaths*”. Figure 2 shows the cascade for this hoax.

Figure 2. Hoax 9 Covid-19: *Es falso que la vacuna contra la covid-19 produzca “decenas de miles de muertos”, como se asegura en una revista*

The influence of this hoax is very different from the last one. The affected channels have escalated to 13 different sources. While widespread, there is no clear ‘super-influence’ in this cascade. “Rafapalreal” appears again with early discussion on the topic, as well as “PADRESPORLAVERDAD”, but they aren’t nearly as influential. Other channels have little involvement like “InfoVacunas”, “Somosrealistas” and “EIcontrafuerte”, with barely a message involved.

Information seems to bounce back and forth between channels, with evenly spread interest across the entire timeline on most channels. Some have periods where they are more active about the topic, for example “ejercitoremanente” discussed heavily about the topic from late 2021 into 2022 summer, while “medicosporlaverdadESP” shows low interest on the topic from late 2021 to December of that same year. Interest in the topic manages to have several overlapping periods of interest that enable the continued interest across the entire timeline.

Finally on Hoax 34: “[Translated] *Pfizer did not commercialize the Covid-19 vaccine without testing its effectiveness*”. This alludes to “*Pfizer sold the vaccine without proper testing*”. Figure 3 shows the cascade for this hoax.

Figure 3. Hoax 34 Covid-19: Pfizer no comercializó la vacuna de la covid sin comprobar su eficacia.

The last example visualization shows a very steady spread of disinformation, where interest is strictly maintained through the entire timeline. This timeline has four channels, however two are extremely relevant while the others barely present any messages. “Rafapalreal” and “PLANDEMIA_MUNDIAL_COVID” contain the entire discussion around this topic, effectively being quarantined to both channels. In this context one channel acts as a sender and the other as a receiver. “PLANDEMIA_MUNDIAL_COVID” constantly and consistently produces messages that link to “rafapalreal”, with barely any inverse interaction. We have seen this trend previously, with “rafapalreal” acting as an aggregator of content and another channel emitting constantly. However, unlike the previous situation, the hoaxes interest never wavers over time, disappearing only due to the data cutoff point.

Despite being contained to these two channels, they have accumulated many views as evidenced by dot size. We conclude that, despite the limited reach of this hoax, it is equally influential in the outside community judging by views, especially due to “rafapalreal”’s outreach with many nodes of larger size.

If evaluated together, some dynamics appear. The transmitter-receiver analogy used earlier, may have grounds for some large-scale dynamic, some channels being authorities that people rely on that people refer to (in order to spread it), and other acts as hubs that accumulate authorities’ knowledge. This is further visualized in Figure 4, where we aggregate all cascades to find the influence flow across the entire timeline. The figure depicts a “who-copies-whom” network, where nodes represent channels and edges indicate influence—that is, when one channel publishes a hoax, another channel tends to publish it as well. The size and saturation of a node indicate its importance within the network: larger and darker nodes are more influential than smaller and lighter ones. Finally, purple nodes are classified as authorities (channels that tend to initiate the propagation process), while orange nodes are classified as hubs (channels that primarily spread or aggregate information originating from authorities).

Figure 4. Covid-19 hubs and authorities

This final observation reveals some super-influential channels. “PADRESPORLAVERDAD” is extremely central to this graph, with a large number of channels referring to it (arrows pointing towards it). The other way around, we observe “elinvestigador_org” as another hub. Only the most influential have been drawn on the graph for the sake of visualization, however, “rafapalreal” also appears as a hub, confirming our previous observations. This network represents the most influential channels of the telegram environment during the mid-2021 to late-2024.

3.2 Climate cascades and influence

The analysis begins on Hoax 18: “[Translated] *The lies of Nobel Giaeever to deny climate change evidence.*”. This alludes to the figure of Ivar Giaeever, nobel prize, who is a common figure amongst climate deniers being himself a figure of authority with climate denier opinions. Figure 5 shows the cascade for this hoax.

Figure 5. Hoax 18 Climate: Las falsedades del nobel Giaeever para negar las evidencias del cambio climático

The graphs generated by the climate change topic are much wider than before. On Covid-19 the search was restricted to a few channels, however, as the search is now free, there are many more channels affected by the hoax. This is a common feature to all visualizations explored in this subsection. The added width of exploration makes for harder analysis.

The cascade for the aforementioned hoax is, instead, about a figure of authority: Ivar Giaeever. His denier claims are numerous, not a singular particular claim. Therefore, what we visualize here is his influence on the climate change discourse across time. Using this frame for analysis, we observe three particular points of interest. June '22, September '22 and late July '23. These three points are characterized by the overwhelming vertical density of posts in the graph. At each one, a lot of channels begin discussing heavily about Giaeever. There are gaps in the discourse surrounding this figure, from October '22 to July '23 there is almost no mention of his, with sporadic interest being shown at best.

There are no clear influencing posts or receivers, just overwhelming cross-posting across channels. We found that most messages during these interest spikes are mostly copy-pasted across channels; meaning they have been spammed across multiple channels. This is particularly interesting during the September '22 spike,

where the messages are mostly identical, but translated across the international community.

It is likely that someone (or a group) has jointly decided to discuss Giaeever across several forums simultaneously to foster discussion and reinforce climate change denial. The triggering incident, if there's any, for these interest spikes are undetermined.

Next is Hoax 43: “[Translated] *It's fake that Spain and 12 additional countries have signed an agreement to abolish agriculture due to climate change.*”. This hoax alludes to a fake bill passed by European countries. Figure 6 illustrates the discourse of this hoax:

Figure 6. Hoax 43 Climate: *Es falso que España y 12 países más hayan firmado un acuerdo para abolir la agricultura por el cambio climático*

Aside from the width of the graph we find some added insights. In particular, in this graph we find a clear discourse leader: “OPERAC_ENJAMBRE”. This channel is the most prolific when talking about this topic, most of its posts influencing outwards the discord from channel to channel; but it also is influenced by other forums in a similar amount. In this sense, it is ambivalent, being both influenced actor and disseminator.

Other prolific channels include “laverdadlibre” for example, but none come close to the designated discourse leader. In fact, we observe that the first message of this hoax was published by the leading channel, which is not usually the case.

Aside from a leader, we find no more meaningful insights, as the hoax is quite short-lived, being fact-checked around June '23 by outlets like [Maldita.es](#) and [Newtral.es](#), which matches the beginning of the life-cycle of the hoax; and finally dies down by January 2024. Compared to other hoaxes, this one is relatively short-lived, considering the time window extends to March '24. Such targeted hoaxes to particular fake legislations end up dying out in favor of newer hoaxes.

Finally we show Hoax 74: “[Translated] *The hockey stick climate graph that represents an unprecedented rise in temperature since the XX century, is reliable.*” (Figure 7). The hockey stick climate graph⁵ alludes to a popular series of data where temperature increases dramatically when observing time from the year 1000 to 2000 (or actuality). The hoax alludes that this particular data is fake, probably used to manipulate the masses.

Figure 7. Hoax 74 Climate: *La gráfica climática del palo de hockey, que representa un aumento de las temperaturas sin precedentes a partir del siglo XX, es fiable*

Again, there is a large breadth of channels in our analysis, but we find some interesting patterns. First, “craigkelly” is a foreign channel, filled with English-speaking users. This channel acts as an influencer on the earlier stages of the hoax from its inception to

⁵ An iteration of the graph: commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:T_comp_61-90.pdf (Note: There are multiple versions of this graph, but the hockey-stick shape prevails)

May '23. Aside from some individual messages posted between November '23 and May '23 (like "PLANDEMIA_MUNDIAL_COVID" in October '23 or "Nuevahumanidadhuelva" in March '23) there is almost no discourse in the Iberian peninsula involving this particular hoax. We entertain the thought that this particular hoax is completely imported from abroad from Anglo-Saxon countries. First, it spawned abroad, then Spanish and Portuguese speaking countries imported this hoax, which is self-evident by "craigkelly" density of comments and the absence of iberian discourse.

Finally, after May '23, the hoax became more widespread, with extremely influential messages from both anglosaxon channels ("brainlesschannel" in May '23) and spanish-speaking channels ("chemtrailsquintacolumna" in early June '23). These super-influential messages spread across the entire graph, almost defining the discourse in its entirety.

To conclude the analysis of hoax 74, it is alarming how misinformation has become increasingly global, to the point of being outright imported from other countries (such as slavic for this analysis). This phenomenon requires further study.

We show the primary actors across all hoaxes in Figure 8, where we examine again the hubs and authorities of climate change discussion. Here we observe the main actors (named vertices) of discourse. In this scenario we find very few hubs, people that consult authorities to publish information, while we find many more authorities.

Figure 8. Climate change hubs and authorities

Hubs (Oranges) / Authorities (Purples)

This imbalance of authorities and hubs is an important point. This means that the misinformation on this topic is frequently ‘cross-pollinated’, where channels ‘make up’ new hoaxes on a regular basis without a clear pattern. There are still some important hubs like “OPERAC_ENJAMBRE” or “nuevahumanidadhuelva” but they aren’t nearly as influential as the largest authorities (like “greatreject”, “euskalnews” or “supercontagiadores”).

3.2 Gender issues cascades and influence

Finally, the graphs for the last set of hoaxes are explored. We begin with hoax 19 depicted in Figure 9: “[Translated] *Sexual aggression in Coimbra University. Is denunciation without names valid during legal processes?*”. This alludes to the hoax that, in Portugal, a sexual violence denouncement can be carried out without naming the victim/aggressor. It is a common trend amongst misogynistic forums to attack laws protecting women’s rights to safety. This hoax falls in line with this particular train of thought.

Figure 9. Hoax 19 Gender: *Assédio sexual na Universidade de Coimbra. Denúncia "sem nomes" é válida em processo legal?*

With this in mind, it stands to reason that the channel “neofeminismo” is the most active around this hoax at the beginning of this hoax lifecycle. This channel is a hotspot for anti-feminist rhetoric, which again, is expected for this hoax. However, other comments don’t fall neatly into this category. For example “cadizcontraelpasaportecovid” is a Covid-19 skeptic group, another completely different topic, but it has still been detected to talk about this issue. Later in the timeline, we find cross-posting during June ‘23 from channels “paremosNewOrdenMundial” and “conscienciaterraplana” which are both conspiracy-theory centric. This is also true for “OPERAC_ENJAMBRE”, which also frequently posts about these issues too. So, it seems that misogyny is widespread in conspiracy theory adjacent channels, as well as covid-denier communities.

The spread of this hoax however is quite subdued. Take note of the low similarity all across the timeline. Thin, transparent lines denote low similarity between posts, meaning that the misogyny trend is loosely connected, but ever-present in these communities. Another reading could be that, because of their loosely related connection to misogyny, their messages aren’t influenced by other channels, instead being influenced mostly by offline opinions. Most of the cascades we have studied so far have many high-similarity connections between messages, so we deem this propagation unusual. We conclude that we do not find this hoax to be evenly propagated at all, instead being disseminated sparsely across time.

Hoax 47 is depicted in Figure 10: “[Translated] *Not a photoshop montage: Cepsa has hung the LGBTI flag on their gas stations*”. This references the common upheaval caused by hanging LGBTI flags, usually carried by homophobia, transphobia and queer-centric hate-speech.

We observe that contagious messages (showing high similarity and high number of outward edges) begin 4 months after the first message on this topic is found. Another example of disjointed discourse. However, this dynamic changes from September ‘22 onwards, where there are many examples of influential messages.

It appears that “ForoPXLVE” leads the discussion, however it is usually influenced by outward channels. On this note, “ForoPXLVE” is a sub-group of “Padres por la verdad” whose influence is negligible in this graph. Most of the crossed activity of this hoax goes from March ‘23 to October ‘23, where very high cross-posting and influence is shared across the entire graph.

Finally, on Figure 11, we analyse hoax 89: “[Translated] *The ‘Only yes is yes’ law won’t demand a sexual consent contract.*” This alludes to a specific law in Spanish courts, that requires enthusiastic consent from both parties to be considered consensual relationships. Right-wing pundits usually rally their followers by claiming that sex will be preceded by a written contract, sometimes in mockery, sometimes (like this hoax) completely straight.

D3.1 - Disinformation on social networks in Spanish and Portuguese Iberian digital media ecosystem

Figure 10. Hoax 47 Gender: *No es un montaje de Photoshop: Cepsa sí ha puesto la bandera LGTBI en sus gasolineras*

Figure 11. Hoax 89 Gender: *La ley de solo sí es sí no exigirá un contrato de consentimiento sexual*

Therefore, taking this narrative into question, it comes as no surprise how “neofeminismo” is the most frequent poster in this hoax again. It’s useful to visualize how the observations from this graph match the observations from the previous misogyny hoax. A heavily disconnected discourse, a mixed bag of actors, it matches step by step. There are some additional observations worth noting. For instance, “ForoPXLVE” reposts frequently in “PADRESPORLAVERDAD” which is expected. Discourse seems even more sparse than before, with some cross-posting associated between channels and little else.

One notable mention is “medicosporlaverdadar” which has a fairly influential message early on in the graph. This is an Argentinian channel vinculated to “medicosporlaverdad” and “PADRESPORLAVERDAD”. In this representation, a hispanic non-iberian channel, has influenced discourse around the issue before it arrived to the iberian peninsula. This is quite the finding, as it proves how interconnected online social networks are, and the *dangers of international misinformation movements*.

Finally, in Figure 12, we show hubs and authorities for gender-issue discourse. As with the previous graph on climate change, the prevalence of authorities is overwhelming. The only hubs “nuevahumanidadhuelva” and “ForoPXLVE” seem to mostly aggregate information about other channels. On the other hand, we see known names, like “PADRESPORLAVERDAD”, “neofeminismo” or “OPERAC_ENJAMBLE” which protagonize some of the discourse.

All taken into account, we draw the same conclusion as with climate change hoaxes, with little variation. This, in itself, is a worthwhile consideration, tightly linking two vastly different topics of discussion under the same explanations may point to the similar ways in which misinformation operates regardless of topics.

Figure 12. Gender issues hubs and authorities

Hubs (Oranges) / Authorities (Purples)

4. Stance detection analysis

The proliferation of misinformation in digital media environments has created an urgent need for systematic approaches to detect and analyze false or misleading content. Disinformation has become one of the main communicative challenges, affecting public perception and decision-making in critical areas such as politics, health, and environment (Organización Mundial de la Salud 2022). It can appear by mistake or with intention, and in times of crisis it compromises social response. Different actors, including governments, political parties, media, corporations, and individuals, act as producers or amplifiers of false content (Salaverria 2025).

Climate disinformation presents particularly complex challenges, taking many forms from direct denial to confusing or alarmist narratives. It includes subtle discourses that recognize the problem but reduce urgency and promote inaction through concepts such as delayism (Fernández Reyes 2024), inactionism and obstructionism (Sánchez & Martín n.d). International institutions like the IPCC and the UN warn that some disinformation is intentional to slow social response (Blanco et. al. 2021), which erodes trust in science. In Spain, one of the most vulnerable countries, while social networks are often considered primary spaces for fake news (Rodrigo-Cano & Del Río Álvarez 2021), traditional and digital news media play equally important roles as they can both share scientific information or amplify disinformation narratives.

This document presents two complementary Large Language Model-based approaches to automated disinformation detection, both applied to climate change narratives within the Iberian digital media ecosystem. The first approach employs thematic clustering before classification to improve the automated detection of disinformation narratives. The second approach implements a stance detection pipeline that leverages a comprehensive database of verified fact-checks from the IBERIFIER fact-checkers network.

The stance detection pipeline builds upon evidence-based verification by integrating artificial intelligence techniques with established fact-checking work. The system's primary objective is to detect instances of previously fact-checked disinformation in news articles and analyze whether these articles support or refute the debunked claims. This approach enables researchers and policymakers to study the spread and persistence of misinformation within digital media ecosystems, specifically for the Iberian context.

Both systems address specific challenges associated with natural language processing in multilingual environments. The technical implementations combine multiple computational approaches including Large Language Models, Retrieval Augmented Generation (RAG) with hybrid retrieval methods, thematic clustering, and specialized stance detection techniques to ensure robust performance across different languages. This document presents the methodological foundations, technical architecture, and operational characteristics of both approaches, focusing on their complementary strengths and performance in detecting climate-related misinformation.

4.1. Thematic clustering for Narrative Detection

Clustering techniques group related elements together. Here, we analyse the stance of texts surrounding weather and climate change discourse. The clustering divided the fakes into two semantic groups. Cluster 0 included affirmations linked to local weather events such as the DANA and references to the AEMET, while cluster 1 focused on structural discourses related to CO2 and climate change. This second cluster was considered a transversal and timeless narrative, not connected to specific meteorological events.

After projection of the 3,006 selected news items onto the semantic space, and after applying stratified filtering, 2,395 news remained (Figure 12). Of these, 930 belonged to cluster 0, centered on local meteorological phenomena, and 1,465 to cluster 1, related to climate change and CO2 emissions. The values of cosine similarity indicated a clear difference: cluster 1 reached higher semantic similarity (max 0.65, mean 0.35) than cluster 0 (max 0.53, mean 0.14). For that reason, cluster 1 was chosen for main analysis.

Figure 12. Projection of digital news in the semantic space created from verified fakes. The news appear as triangles with colors according to their cluster. The shaded circles show the reference fakes, and the crosses mark the centroids of each group.

Classification Performance Results (Figure 13): Scenario A gave the best results: $F1 = 0.79$, with strong performance in REFUTE ($F1 = 0.90$). Scenario B had lower accuracy ($F1 = 0.46$), and scenario C was intermediate ($F1 = 0.58$). The results demonstrate that thematic clustering, especially combined with semantic filtering, improves the narrative precision of the system.

Figure 13: Confusion matrix for scenario A: news close to the fake. Most of the news labeled as REFUTE were classified correctly by the model. The IGNORE and SUPPORT classes were less precise.

The superior performance of Scenario A ($F1 = 0.79$) compared to scenarios without clustering demonstrates the effectiveness of combining thematic organization with semantic similarity filtering. The strong performance in the REFUTE category ($F1 = 0.90$) indicates that the system successfully identifies news articles that contradict climate disinformation narratives. This approach proves particularly valuable for detecting content that actively counters false climate claims.

4.2. Generative approach for stance detection

We evaluate generative LLMs for multilingual stance detection across five prompting strategies, four models, and two datasets (SemEval-2016 in EN; CIC in ES/CAT). Performance is reported as macro-F1 over favor /against.

Evaluation of Open-Source LLMs. With English-only prompting, few-shot and the mCoS consistently outperform other schemes on small models. Qwen-7B (mCoS) yields the best small-model averages (SemEval: 72.21%; CIC: 50.82%) and exceeds prior SOTA on CC (78.88%) and HC (77.60%); Mistral-7B few-shot leads CIC-ES (53.10%). Prompting in the dataset's native language (ES/CAT) lowers scores: the best in-language mCoS reaches CIC-ES: 48.99%, CIC-CAT: 50.23%, CIC Avg: 49.61%, indicating a strong English bias. This summary is visualized in Figure 14.

Figure 14: F1-score comparison across supervised baselines (TF-IDF + SVM, mBERT, XLM-R) and the best-performing generative LLM setup for each dataset.⁶

Scaling up improves results substantially. Qwen-72B (mCoS) attains 76.89% on SemEval and 62.98% CIC average, surpassing SOTA in most categories (e.g., CC: 88.55%, CIC-ES: 68.14%, CIC-CAT: 57.82%); Mistral-24B also posts gains (AT: 74.15% with mCoS; HC: 87.72% with few-shot). Against supervised baselines, Qwen-72B (mCoS) outperforms all finetuned models on SemEval, but on CIC the

⁶ While the LLM surpasses all baselines on the English SemEval-2016 dataset, it underperforms on the multilingual CIC-ES and CIC-CAT datasets.

finetuned encoders (mBERT/XLM-R) exceed 74%, remaining superior in non-English settings. (See Tables 7–9 and Fig. X.)

Table 7: English Prompting results⁷.

Model	Prompting	LA	AT	CC	FM	HC	SemEval Avg	CIC-ES	CIC-CAT	CIC Avg
Mistral-7B	Zero-Shot	50.53	23.55	74.04	54.81	61.94	56.29	48.77	43.28	48.77
	Few-Shot	66.77	25.82	74.88	58.08	60.38	60.05	53.10	44.52	48.81
	Chain-of-Thought	51.58	26.21	<u>76.05</u>	55.98	55.19	55.09	46.81	41.40	44.11
	Chain-of-Stance	46.69	31.98	70.99	61.65	<u>67.08</u>	59.26	51.95	<u>47.44</u>	<u>49.70</u>
	COLA	64.28	<u>37.10</u>	58.10	<u>62.26</u>	64.46	<u>63.86</u>	49.96	46.16	48.06
Qwen-7B	Zero-Shot	52.27	34.99	67.38	68.37	75.08	64.13	35.56	36.35	36.00
	Few-Shot	58.39	49.28	64.23	66.62	68.75	65.59	45.53	43.70	44.62
	Chain-of-Thought	53.85	27.46	67.85	67.76	72.77	62.39	32.97	34.08	33.53
	Chain-of-Stance	57.09	60.84	78.88	68.77	<u>77.60</u>	72.21	<u>52.59</u>	49.05	50.82
	COLA	<u>59.68</u>	51.86	59.43	62.95	<u>76.41</u>	68.27	44.73	48.31	46.52
Stance Reasoner (SOTA)		74.30	72.00	60.00	74.00	76.10	75.10	49.50	55.40	52.45

Ablation Study of Modified Variant of Chain of Stance. We ablated each step of the modified CoS using Qwen-72B on SemEval-2016 and CIC (Table 10). The full CoS yields the best CIC results (CIC-ES: 68.14%; CIC Avg: 62.54%), and removing steps generally degrades performance, indicating additive value. Exceptions are dataset-specific: on CIC-CAT, every ablation slightly improves over the full method (best 59.28% when dropping Context Understanding); on SemEval-2016, removing Context Understanding gives the top average (78.06%). Effects vary by target with no consistent pattern. Notably, removing Logical Inference has no impact anywhere, so it can be omitted for efficiency without loss. Overall, most steps help, but gains are dataset and category-dependent; the full pipeline, minus Logical Inference, is the most reliable.

Table 8: In-Language Prompting results⁸.

Model	Prompting	SemEval Avg	CIC-ES	CIC-CAT	CIC Avg
Mistral-7B	Zero-Shot	56.29	47.55	49.90	<u>48.73</u>
	Few-Shot	60.05	47.25	<u>50.11</u>	48.68
	Chain-of-Thought	55.09	45.95	47.68	46.82
	Chain-of-Stance	59.26	<u>48.28</u>	46.38	47.33
	COLA	<u>63.86</u>	45.52	42.79	44.16
Qwen-7B	Zero-Shot	64.13	35.30	42.55	38.93
	Few-Shot	65.59	47.06	46.99	47.03
	Chain-of-Thought	62.39	31.66	42.49	37.08
	Chain-of-Stance	72.21	48.99	50.23	49.61
	COLA	68.27	41.30	41.55	41.43
Stance Reasoner (SOTA)	Few Shot	75.10	51.60	50.60	51.10

Table 9: F1-scores of supervised baselines versus best-performing LLM setups. Qwen-72B for the SemEval- 2016 and CIC corpus using CoS method.

⁷ F1 scores (in percentages) for each prompting method and model across all SemEval-2016 targets and CIC datasets. The Stance Reasoner baseline is included for comparison. SemEval Avg is the average F1 over the five SemEval categories; CIC Avg is the mean of CIC-ES and CIC-CAT scores. Bold indicates the best score in each column. Underline is the best score per model. Bold and underlined surpasses SOTA.

⁸ F1-scores (in percentages) for each prompting method across SemEval- 2016 and the CIC. Bold indicates the best score in each column. Underline is the best score per model. Bold and underlined surpasses SOTA.

System	SemEval-2016 Avg ⁹	CIC-ES ⁷	CIC-CAT ⁷
TF-IDF + SVM	63.38	71.09	70.90
mBERT (msl 256, batch 32, lr 5e-5, 5e)	68.10	74.72	74.08
XLM-R (msl 128, batch 16, lr 2e-5, 10e)	70.17	73.57	74.68
Best LLM (for comparison)	76.89	<u>68.14</u>	<u>57.82</u>

Dataset and LLM Logic Analysis. We manually analyzed 100 Spanish and 100 Catalan tweets from the CIC dataset, focusing on misclassifications made by the Qwen-72B model under the modified CoS prompting method (previously the best-performing setup). The annotator—a native Catalan speaker and trained NLP engineer—categorized each error as either dataset-related or model-related.

Dataset-related error categories included: annotator error (incorrect labels), totally unrelated (not about the independence movement), and ambiguous tweets (too vague for reliable labeling). Model-related errors were: missing conversation structure (reply-dependent meaning), contextual misinterpretation (failure to capture cultural/political nuance), and sentiment analysis error (misreading tone or intent).

For Spanish tweets, most errors were dataset-related: 42% annotator errors, 21% unrelated, and 11% ambiguous. Only 26% stemmed from model reasoning (Figure 15). Catalan tweets showed a similar pattern: 39.4% annotator errors, 18.2% unrelated, and 13.1% ambiguous (Figure 15). Correcting annotation issues and removing unrelated tweets reclassified 42 of 100 Spanish and 39 of 100 Catalan misclassifications.

Figure 15: Pie charts showing the distribution of labeled misclassifications for Spanish and Catalan tweets in the CIC dataset using the Qwen-72B Chain-of-Stance method.

In the full datasets, the most frequent Spanish errors were Against→None (151), Favor→None (150), and Against→Favor (97). In Catalan, the largest errors were Against→Favor (330), Favor→Against (183), and Against→None (115). Notably, the model often over-inferred pro-independence stance from Catalan-language tweets.

RT @JCM Cat: La resposta de la GC que ha difo s l'escamot de suport! Ara, el paio no s'acosta a l'artefacte, eh!

(Translation: The GC response that the support squad has spread! Now, the guy doesn't go near the artifact, huh!)

⁹ Supervised scores are reported from (Zotova et al. 2021).

This tweet was originally labeled as None, yet the model predicted it as Favor. In its mCoS reasoning, the model inferred a high probability of a pro-independence stance, citing the language, sociopolitical context, and skeptical tone. Notably, the model explicitly justified its prediction as follows:

The stance most logically supported by the text is FAVOR towards the Catalan independence movement. Here’s why:

Language and Context: The tweet is written in Catalan, which is a strong indicator of alignment with the Catalan independence movement. The use of Catalan language in this context is significant because it is often associated with Catalan nationalism and the independence movement.

Content and Tone: The tweet shares a response from the Mossos d’Esquadra (Catalan police) regarding an incident involving an independentist group. The tone is skeptical and critical of the police’s actions, which suggests a supportive stance towards the independentist group. The phrase “eh!” at the end of the tweet adds a dismissive tone, indicating that the author does not fully trust or accept the police’s response.

While the reasoning appears coherent, the prediction overlooks the fact that language use alone is not a reliable indicator of political stance. The tweet does not explicitly express support for independence, and the model’s overreliance on linguistic and tonal signals—such as assuming Catalan equals Favor—demonstrates a form of stereotyping.

Overall, results indicate that dataset noise—labeling inconsistencies and low-quality annotations—accounts for a substantial share of misclassifications, overshadowing model reasoning flaws. This contrasts with the better-curated SemEval-2016 dataset, where prior work (Taranukhin et al., 2024) identified far fewer annotation errors.

Table 10: Ablation study of the modified CoS reasoning steps on Qwen-72B. Results are F1 scores (in percentages) for SemEval-2016 and CIC datasets. Bold numbers are ablations that outperformed the Full CoS Method.

Configuration	LA	AT	CC	FM	HC	SemEval Avg	CIC-ES	CIC-CAT	CIC Avg
Full CoS	68.12	74.14	88.55	72.17	77.82	76.89	68.14	57.82	62.54
Without Context Understanding	66.58	74.84	86.90	74.00	84.33	78.06	62.35	59.28	60.82
Without Viewpoint Extraction	68.58	71.15	89.11	70.83	76.55	75.96	66.66	58.42	62.39
Without Sentiment Analysis	67.30	72.04	88.73	72.41	77.49	76.29	66.72	58.36	62.54
Without Stance Comparison	68.61	52.38	84.62	72.75	79.02	75.04	60.17	58.42	59.30
Without Logical Inference	68.12	74.14	88.55	72.17	77.82	76.89	68.14	57.82	62.54

4.2.1 Discussion

The results of this study demonstrate that instruction-tuned LLMs can be highly competitive with supervised methods in English, but their effectiveness decreases in multilingual contexts. On the SemEval-2016 dataset, Qwen-72B with mCoS prompting achieved a macro-F1 of 76.89%, surpassing supervised baselines and showing that generative models, when guided by well-structured prompts, can match or exceed fine-tuned approaches without labeled data. In contrast, performance on the Catalonia Independence Corpus (CIC) averaged 62.98%, falling short of fine-tuned multilingual

baselines such as mBERT and XLM-R, which achieved over 74%. This suggests that while larger LLMs benefit from broader pretraining and demonstrate stronger generalization, fine-tuning remains critical in low-resource and culturally specific settings.

Prompting strategies played a decisive role across experiments. Few-shot and mCoS prompting consistently outperformed zero-shot, CoT, and COLA methods, particularly for smaller models. The strength of the mCoS method lies in decomposing stance detection into structured reasoning steps, which both improved performance and enhanced interpretability. By generating contextual background information about the tweet, its author, and audience before proceeding to sentiment and stance evaluation, mCoS provided models with implicit world knowledge that improved classification accuracy, especially in Spanish and Catalan. This aligns with supervised approaches that incorporate external knowledge sources and highlights the importance of contextual grounding in multilingual stance detection. Another advantage of mCoS is transparency: by exposing intermediate reasoning steps, it allows researchers to pinpoint where the model's logic fails and refine prompts accordingly.

At the same time, our analysis uncovered systematic biases. In CIC-CAT, the model often inferred proindependence stance solely from the use of Catalan language, reflecting a linguistic bias rooted in pretraining data. While the reasoning appeared coherent, predictions frequently relied on language as a proxy for political stance, illustrating the risk of stereotyping and underscoring the need for multilingual fairness audits when deploying LLMs in politically sensitive contexts.

Dataset quality emerged as another major factor influencing results. Manual error analysis showed that around 60% of misclassifications in both Spanish and Catalan stemmed from incorrect labels or unrelated tweets, with an additional 11–13% too ambiguous for reliable human annotation. This suggests that LLM performance was likely underestimated due to dataset noise. These problems stem from the CIC dataset's semi-automatic annotation strategy, which assigned stance labels at the user level rather than per tweet. In contrast, SemEval-2016 was manually labeled at the tweet level, offering greater reliability. This finding highlights the critical importance of high-quality, carefully annotated datasets for both training and evaluation, especially in tasks where stance can be subtle or ambiguous.

Taken together, the findings suggest that stance detection is a particularly challenging but valuable benchmark for LLM evaluation. Unlike common reasoning tasks, it requires models to integrate tone, emotion, cultural nuance, and sociopolitical context—making it especially suitable for testing higher-order reasoning and multilingual robustness. Given its real-world applications in areas such as misinformation detection, political analysis, and content moderation, the consequences of misclassification are nontrivial, and stance detection deserves greater attention in benchmark design.

Nevertheless, several limitations constrain the present study. The evaluation was limited to four open-source LLMs, five prompting methods, English, Spanish, and Catalan data, and tweet-length inputs. Results may not generalize to other languages, scripts, or longer and more formal texts. Moreover, the manual error audit covered

only 200 tweets, representing a fraction of the CIC dataset. Broader re-annotation and expansion to more diverse languages would strengthen future analyses.

Finally, ethical considerations must be taken into account. Misclassifying stance in politically sensitive domains risks reinforcing polarization or enabling text-based censorship. Biases, such as associating Catalan language use with pro-independence stance, illustrate the dangers of cultural stereotyping. In addition, the environmental costs of running large-scale inference with massive models raise questions about sustainability and responsible research practices. Greater transparency and accountability—through open datasets, shared prompts, and interpretable reasoning methods—are essential to ensure that stance detection systems can be applied fairly and responsibly in real-world contexts.

These results were used to determine our course of action for the full Iberifier pipeline, which used our modified Chain-of-Stance prompting methods, which yielded the overall best results in English, Spanish, and Catalan and we used the Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct model which achieved the highest scores in a multilingual context. The model implementation details were applied the same as the methodology section.

4.3. Stance Detection Pipeline with Hybrid Retrieval

This analysis processed 16,249 articles from 1,594 newspapers collected between January and April 2025, including both national and regional sources and providing broad geographical coverage across Spanish-speaking countries. The system extracted 326,671 statements and 267,712 (82%) successfully matched with relevant fact-checks and received stance classifications from 5,516 unique fact-checks from five organizations: EFE Verifica, Maldita.es, Newtral, Polígrafo, and Verificat (see Figure 16).

Figure 16: Stance distribution for all sources and Iberifier digital media list.

(a) All sources (n=267,712 stance results)

(b) Iberifier digital media list (n=11,195 stance results)

4.3.1 Dataset Comparison

All stance distributions use FINAL stance after consistency validation. Initial statement-level classifications (SUPPORTS 20.1%, REFUTES 15.1%, NOT_RELATED 64.7%) were refined through article-context re-evaluation to produce more conservative final stances. To validate stance classifications, the pipeline re-evaluates stances using full article context:

- Consistency rate: 82.1% (all sources), 81.8% (Iberifier digital media list)
- Change types: Most changes are clarifications (NOT_RELATED → SUPPORTS/REFUTES)
- Critical reversals: SUPPORTS ↔ REFUTES occur in only 2.3% of cases

Table 11 presents key metrics for both datasets and Figure 17, the change per label in both the full dataset and the dataset filtered using the Iberian digital media list.

Figure 17: Stance transition matrices showing consistency validation results. Diagonal dominance indicates high consistency rates (82.1% all sources, 81.8% Iberifier digital media list). Most changes represent clarifications from NOT_RELATED to specific stances rather than critical SUPPORTS↔REFUTES reversals.

(a) All sources (n=214,062)

(b) Iberifier digital media list (n=9,034)

Table 11: Dataset overview. Stance distributions use FINAL stance after consistency validation.

Metric	All Sources	Iberifier digital media list
Total articles	16,249	643
Total newspapers	1,594	84
Total statements	326,671	13,882
Avg statements/article	20.1	21.6
Stance Distribution (FINAL)		
SUPPORTS	15.8%	15.9%
REFUTES	9.9%	10.1%
NOT_RELATED	74.3%	74.0%
Consistency Validation		
Consistency rate	82.1%	81.8%

4.3.2 Analysis of stance detection

Of the 326,671 total extracted statements, 267,712 (82%) successfully matched with relevant fact-checks and received stance classifications.

The extraction of claim statements from news articles shows that on average an article contains 20.1 statements (all sources), 21.6 statements (Iberifier digital media list), see Figure 18.

Figure 18: Distribution of statements per article (all sources, n=16,249 articles).

The type of fact-checks retrieved were primarily False (49%), Explainer (26%) and Misleading (15%), see Figure.

Across all sources, 15.8% of statements SUPPORT fact-checks classified as “Falso” (see Figure 19) in legitimate media channels. To examine whether supporting and refuting stances vary in their placement throughout news articles, we analyzed the position of each stance-bearing statement within its article (0% = beginning, 100% = end). This analysis investigates whether media outlets strategically position fact-check-related content in prominent locations (headlines, leads) or bury it in later paragraphs.

Figure 19: Stance distributions by fact-check qualification type (all sources). Critical finding: 15.8% of statements SUPPORT fact-checks classified as “Falso” (debunked claims), indicating problematic misinformation propagation through

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media coverage. Conversely, “Verdadero” (true) claims receive 33.7% support, demonstrating truth amplification.

Analysis of stance positioning reveals uniform distribution throughout article structure, with SUPPORTS stances appearing at a mean position of 53.4% (median 50.0%, SD 31.1%) and REFUTES stances at 52.8% (median 50.0%, SD 30.6%). Both stance types distribute evenly across all article positions, from opening paragraphs through closing sections. This uniform distribution indicates no headline bias: supporting and refuting statements are not preferentially placed in prominent article positions such as headlines, leads, or conclusions. Rather, stances appear integrated throughout article structure, suggesting content integration rather than strategic framing see Figure 20.

Figure 20: Distribution of stance positions within articles. Kernel density estimation shows positioning for SUPPORTS and REFUTES stances, revealing uniform distribution across article structure (mean 53%, median 50%) with no concentration in headlines or conclusions.

(a) All sources

(b) Iberifier digital media list

4.3.3 Article-Level Stance Coverage

To understand how stances are distributed across articles, we examined the number of unique stance types present in each article and the number of stance analyses performed per article. This analysis investigates whether articles contain mixed stances or predominantly exhibit single stance types.

Analysis of article-level stance coverage reveals that most articles contain multiple statements with stance classifications but exhibit limited diversity in stance types. For all sources, the majority of articles contain between 1-4 stance analyses per article, though a substantial number contain 10 or more analyses reflecting longer articles with more claim statements. Regarding unique stance types, most articles exhibit 1-2 different stance types rather than all three possible stances (SUPPORTS, REFUTES, NOT_RELATED). This pattern indicates that while articles may contain multiple analyzed statements, they tend to maintain relatively consistent positioning rather than presenting highly mixed or contradictory stances within the same article. The Iberifier digital media list shows similar patterns, with comparable distributions of stance coverage and unique stance types, suggesting that these article-level structural characteristics are consistent across different media outlet types (see Figure 21).

Figure 21: Article-level stance coverage showing (left) distribution of unique stance types per article and (right) distribution of total stance analyses per article. Most articles contain multiple stance analyses, with the majority exhibiting 1-2 unique stance types, indicating mixed content rather than uniform positioning.

4.3.4 Article-Level Aggregated Patterns

To complement statement-level analysis, we examined article-level aggregate patterns by computing continuous positioning scores for each article. Articles receive scores ranging from -1 (complete refutation) to +1 (complete support) based on the mean of all detected stances (SUPPORTS = +1, NOT_RELATED = 0, REFUTES = -1). This approach captures nuanced article positioning beyond binary classification.

Analysis of 16,249 articles reveals predominantly neutral positioning across the corpus. The mean aggregate score of 0.045 (after consistency validation) indicates slight overall supportive bias, though the magnitude suggests minimal practical

significance. Approximately 88.4% of articles showed mixed or neutral positioning (scores between -0.5 and +0.5), with only 6.7% predominantly supportive (scores > 0.5) and 4.9% predominantly refutative (scores < -0.5). The consistency validation process reduced supportive positioning, with 54.0% of articles becoming more refutative or less supportive through contextual re-evaluation, demonstrating the value of article-context validation.

Substantial newspaper variation emerges at the article aggregate level, with mean scores ranging from -0.347 to +0.385 across newspapers with sufficient article counts. However, high within-newspaper standard deviations (typically 0.24-0.31) indicate that individual article variability exceeds outlet-level effects. Topic-dependent positioning patterns are evident, with climate denial and renewable energy opposition queries showing supportive positioning (mean scores 0.124 and 0.089), while climate action advocacy and fact-checking promotion queries showed refutative positioning (mean scores -0.038 and -0.094). Monthly trends remained stable throughout the study period (January-April 2025), with mean scores ranging only from 0.043 to 0.061, indicating consistent patterns rather than temporal shifts in media positioning.

To understand outlet-specific behaviors, we calculated stance rates per article for each newspaper with sufficient article coverage.

For each newspaper, we computed the SUPPORTS rate per article, Total SUPPORTS stances (using FINAL stance) divided by total articles and the REFUTES rate (same formula but with the REFUTES counts). These metrics represent the average number of supporting or refuting stances per article for each outlet. Figure 22 shows the top 10 newspapers by article count..

Figure 22: Stance rates by newspaper (top 10 by article count). The figure shows the average number of SUPPORTS and REFUTES stances per article for each outlet. Substantial variation reveals heterogeneity in positioning patterns across different newspapers. The name of the outlet is anonymised as the data collection is not representative.

Analysis reveals substantial heterogeneity in stance patterns across individual newspapers, with widely varying rates of supporting and refuting stances per

article. Some newspapers consistently show higher engagement with fact-check-related content, demonstrating outlet-specific patterns that reflect editorial priorities and content strategies. Importantly, database-level aggregation obscures these important outlet-specific differences, indicating no systematic bias at the aggregate level. This heterogeneity underscores that editorial policy, topic specialization, and ownership structure drive positioning patterns more strongly than database membership.

4.3.5 Iberifier Digital media list

Concentrating the analysis on the Iberifier digital media list, the results show a broad media landscape, internal variation within the Iberifier digital media list group is substantial, with individual outlets ranging widely in their positioning patterns. Analysis indicates that editorial policy and topic specialization appear to influence positioning more strongly than database membership, and no systematic bias toward supporting or refuting fact-checked claims emerges at the database level.

The 15.8% support rate for debunked claims (“Falso”) is noteworthy, as it suggests potential pathways for misinformation propagation through legitimate media channels. However, the 9.9% overall refutation rate (FINAL stance) and uniform stance positioning suggest active debunking efforts without strategic framing biases.

4.3.6 Discussion

The stance detection pipeline employs a systematic approach to identifying and analyzing the spread of misinformation within the Iberian digital media ecosystem. By combining verified fact-checks from established organizations with advanced computational techniques, the system enables large-scale analysis of how claims are mentioned, framed, and circulated within digital media. The hybrid retrieval strategy, statement-level granularity, and distributed processing architecture provide a replicable framework for examining misinformation patterns across the multilingual Iberian context.

The system is designed to be open source and modular, allowing researchers and practitioners to extend its capabilities beyond the current focus and ingest other types of structured and unstructured data. This adaptability ensures that the framework can evolve with the needs of the research and policy community while supporting comparative studies across domains. Moreover, the pipeline is implemented as a full retrieval-augmented generation (RAG) system built upon the existing Iberifier database, enabling fact-checkers to integrate large language models (LLMs) into their established workflows. This facilitates not only more efficient retrieval and contextualization of relevant claims but also supports evidence-based reasoning aligned with fact-checking practices.

Several directions are identified to further strengthen the pipeline’s impact and applicability:

- **Automating data ingestion:** Streamlining the integration of new fact-checks from the Iberifier database into the RAG system to ensure continuous updates and minimize manual intervention.
- **Enhancing stance detection:** Improving the stance detection models, with particular focus on the internal consistency of outputs and robustness across diverse media contexts.
- **Cross-lingual verification:** Developing methods to identify and analyze whether claims and fact-checks propagate across languages, thereby capturing misinformation dynamics in the broader Iberian context.
- **Portuguese media integration:** Expanding the pipeline to systematically test and analyze the Portuguese media landscape, complementing the current emphasis on Spanish and Catalan sources.
- **Geographic and origin analysis:** Incorporating more refined tools to examine the provenance of fact-checks, their original sources, and the geographic distribution of the digital media in which they circulate.
- **Enhancing the IBERIFIER database:** While the information contained in the IBERIFIER database is well defined, there is room to improve the different consistency of fields to ensure a common understanding of the different fields. The use of the field debunked, should become systematic and offer a clear distinction between the claim, its context and the information added by the fact-checkers.

These developments aim to extend the system's scientific value, ensuring broader coverage, higher accuracy, and deeper insights into the mechanisms of misinformation in multilingual and cross-national contexts.

5. The spread of misinformation on Twitter

5.1 Data Collection and Misinformation Identification

As mentioned, we used the GlobalClaims¹⁰ dataset (Vranic et. al. 2025), collected and curated by the Social Physics and Complexity (SPAC) team at LIP. This is a collection of 67,000 fact-checked claims published between 2015 and 2023 by over 100 fact-checking organisations worldwide. This dataset provides the original verdict for each claim, as well as a normalised veracity category mapped to a unique scale across different fact-checker categories (true, false, other, and satire). In addition to veracity labels, the dataset also included thematic classification across 22 subtopics, grouped under six broader domains: Politics, Health, Environment, Science and Society. Each claim is also associated with its source URL, enabling further analysis of the spread of these claims on social media platforms.

For the purpose of this study, the analysis focused on *false* claims fact-checked by organisations based in Spain, Brazil, and several Spanish-speaking countries, including Chile, Mexico, and Venezuela. These countries were selected due to their media relevance within the Iberian and Latin American information ecosystem. The thematic scope was limited to claims related to *Covid-19 and Environmental* issues, two domains that generated large amounts of misinformation activity across social platforms in the past decade. The distribution of claims across fact-checkers, countries, and thematic categories is summarised in Table 12 below.

Table 12: Number of false Covid-19 and Environmental claims analysed by fact-checkers in Spanish- and Portuguese-speaking countries.

Fact-Checker	Country	N Covid claims	N Environment claims
Maldita.es	Spain	13	0
AFP Checamos (Brazil)	Brazil	164	45
Comprova	Brazil	90	35
Agência Lupa	Brazil	3	4
AFP Factual	Spanish-speaking Countries	302	237
Mala Espina Check	Chile	23	26
FastCheckCL	Chile	23	12
Telemundo	Florida (Latin community)	19	2

In total, the selected subset includes over 1000 claims across both topics, with a predominance of Covid-19-related misinformation verified by Brazilian and regional Latin American fact-checkers. Environmental misinformation, while less frequent, is more analysed by Spanish-language outlets.

¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1145/3746275.3762201>

5.2 Spread of fact-checked claims on Twitter

To understand how verified misinformation circulates on social networks, we analysed the diffusion of fact-checked claims on Twitter. Using the Academic Twitter API, we collected all publicly available posts containing URLs corresponding to fact-checked claims verified by fact-checking organisations in Portuguese- and Spanish-speaking countries. The dataset collection lasted until June 2023, when the Academic API was discontinued.

In total, we collected approximately 20,000 tweets, including original posts and their associated retweets. Each tweet was categorised according to the claim's topic (*Covid-19* or *Environment*) and whether a Portuguese or Spanish fact-checking organisation analysed it. The tables below display the false claims mostly shared on Twitter by language (Spanish and Portuguese) and topic (*Covid-19* and *Environment*) (Tables 13A-13D).

Table 13A: Collected false Covid-19 claims in Spanish		
N	Claim	N tweets
1	El Gobierno paraliza en Zaragoza 5.000 kilos de mascarillas para Madrid porque «Aduanas cierra a las 15h»	4069
2	Celáa y Valerio, Ministras y ex ministras de Sánchez se pusieron guantes de látex el 8M por miedo al coronavirus	676
3	Whatspp cede a las presiones del Gobierno y limita el reenvío de mensajes durante la cuarentena	416
4	Las vacunas del COVID-19 magnetizan a las personas.	361
5	“LA BANCA ROTHSCHILD REGISTRÓ HACE CINCO AÑOS UN MÉTODO PARA TESTEAR EL COVID-19”	308
6	Anuncia Cuba que fabricó vacuna contra el coronavirus	200
7	La FDA acaba de actualizar su postura sobre las PCR y no volverán a ser usadas en Estados Unidos EEUU	184
8	Murió más gente por las vacunas contra la COVID-19 en estos tres meses en EEUU que en la última década	89
9	Nuevo estudio evidencia relación covid-19 y la radiación 5G	55
10	La crisis del coronavirus rebaja en Italia el número de políticos	31
11	No es sano respirar CO2 dióxido de carbono. "USO RACIONAL DE LAS MASCARILLAS"	21
12	"(Las recomendaciones para prevenir el COVID-19) son profundamente anticientíficas que se enfocan en un control absoluto del Gobierno sobre cada aspecto de nuestras vidas".	17
13	Los vacunados tienen una carga viral 251 veces superior de coronavirus que los no vacunados contra el covid-19	16
14	Una empleada de Pfizer confirma que la vacuna contiene nanopartículas de óxido de grafeno	12
15	El gobierno británico reconoce en un documento oficial que el resurgimiento tanto de las hospitalizaciones como de las muertes está dominado por los que han recibido dos dosis de la vacuna.	12
16	La ivermectina sirve para tratar el COVID-19.	11
17	"Afortunadamente, mientras el virus comenzó a extenderse, el presidente actuó rápido para asegurar que los ventiladores fueran a los hospitales que más los necesitaban"	11

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Table 13B: Collected Environment claims in Spanish		
N	Claim	N tweets
1	CAYÓ UN METEORITO EN LAS COSTAS DE ANTOFAGASTA DURANTE LOS SISMOS Y FALSA ALERTA DE LA ONEMI	1274
2	“ESTADO DE CHILE PAGARÁ SUELDO MENSUAL A LA EMPRESA AES GENER DURANTE 5 AÑOS PARA QUE CIERRE SU TERMOELÉCTRICA”	37
3	“Puerto Rico ha recibido 91.000 millones de dólares por el huracán, más dinero del que nunca se ha obtenido por un huracán antes”	15

Table 13C: Collected Covid-19 claims in Portuguese		
N	Claim	N tweets
1	Senador Randolfe promete comendas a médicos do Amapá pelo que chamou de heróico combate a Covid-19. Detalhes: eles trataram com hidroxcloroquina, ivermectina, vitamina D e mais. Vai condecorar?	3170
2	Homem de 33 anos sofre grave acidente de moto. Houve traumatismo cranioencefálico. O óbito foi por Covid-19	2002
3	Maior estudo retrospectivo em pacientes hospitalizados mostra que a hidroxcloroquina reduz significativamente o risco de mortalidade por covid-19	1423
4	O uso de máscaras não reduz o risco de contrair o coronavírus e é prejudicial à saúde	477
5	Hospital Unimed-Rio cura covid-19 do paciente Antônio Carlos,67, com cloroquina	314
6	Cientistas afirmaram que sol do meio-dia é extremamente eficaz na erradicação do vírus. Segundo o estudo, o sol mata o coronavírus em 34 minutos.	101
7	Bolsonaro recusou um contrato de 70 milhões de doses de vacina até dezembro/21 em prol de um contrato de 100 milhões de doses até SETEMBRO/21. O que a mídia faz? Divulga só a primeira metade da notícia.	95
8	Pessoas com lúpus não desenvolvem Covid-19	63
9	Usar máscaras é destruir mais ainda com a sua imunidade	62
10	OMS alerta sobre máscaras infectadas que chegam ao Brasil	53
11	Médico do Hospital Municipal Ronaldo Gazzola, no Rio de Janeiro, defende o fim da quarentena	42
12	Dez artistas morreram de covid mesmo após tomar Coronavac	34
13	Variante Delta é menos agressiva, vacinas não protegem contra ela e crianças não transmitem o vírus	28
14	Médica afirma em vídeo que a covid-19 pode ser curada com a ivermectina, remédio usado para tratar parasitas	22

Table 13D: Collected Environmental claims in Portuguese		
N	Claim	N tweets
1	Madeira ilegal apreendida no Pará pelo Exército seria de fundador de uma ONG ligada à proteção ambiental na Amazônia, que também teria envolvimento com o MST no estado.	599
2	Arrozeiros de Roraima viram as áreas plantadas encolherem pela metade depois da demarcação da Terra Indígena Raposa Serra do Sol	590
3	Amazônia não está queimando, Brasil é o país que mais preserva áreas nativas do mundo e alimentos brasileiros são os mais sustentáveis do planeta	246

Table 13D: Collected Environmental claims in Portuguese		
N	Claim	N tweets
4	o maquinário que os chineses estão usando para fazer a estrada de ferro que vai da região de Lucas do Rio Verde	202
5	Sérgio Moro tem o aval legal para mandar a Polícia Federal investigar o Greenpeace	107
6	STF vai "constitucionalmente" cuidar do meio ambiente	69
7	Técnicos da Anvisa liberaram agrotóxicos banidos na Europa mas não a importação da vacina Sputnik V. Não é politização, é coincidência...	21

From these tables, several patterns emerge. First, Covid-19 misinformation dominates in both the number of unique claims and their overall diffusion. Spanish and Portuguese claims share similar narratives, vaccine scepticism, and distrust in health authorities. The most viral claim in Portuguese promoted treatments such as ivermectin or hydroxychloroquine, whereas in Spanish, it focused on the use of masks and government actions in deploying them. In contrast, environmental misinformation is less frequent. Spanish-language examples often exploit local events, such as meteorite sightings or regional energy policies, while Portuguese claims focus on Amazon deforestation and governmental regulation.

5.2 Properties of Twitter Cascades

A **Twitter cascade** is defined as a chain of retweets originating from an initial post that shared a given claim's URL. By analysing these cascades, we can quantify the replication and visibility of claims through user engagement. Figure 23 shows the number of cascades per URL source shared on Twitter.

Figure 23: Number of cascades per source which were shared on Twitter. Please note the difference in scale (log, x-axis).

The structural properties of misinformation diffusion on Twitter were analysed by examining the cascade size distributions (i.e., the total number of tweets in one cascade) for both topics (*Covid-19* and *Environment*) in Portuguese and Spanish. The resulting distributions, shown in Figure 24, were fitted to a power-law function of the form $P(k) \sim k^{-\gamma}$, where $P(k)$ denotes the probability of observing a cascade of size k , and γ is the scaling exponent. This model is often used to describe heavy-tailed diffusion processes in social media environments, where a small number of events achieve disproportionate amplification while most receive minimal engagement.

As expected, the distributions exhibit a heavy-tailed pattern across all languages and topics, suggesting that most misinformation claims generated small cascades, while a limited subset achieved widespread diffusion. For COVID-19 misinformation, both Portuguese and Spanish datasets contained substantially more cascades than their environmental counterparts—1,097 cascades in Portuguese ($\gamma = 1.58$) and 1,119 cascades in Spanish ($\gamma = 2.31$). Environmental misinformation produced fewer cascades overall—926 in Portuguese ($\gamma = 3.28$) and 154 in Spanish ($\gamma = 4.9$).

Figure 24: Probability distribution (PDF) of cascade sizes for claims classified as false within the Covid-19 and Environment topics, in Spanish and Portuguese. Distributions are fitted with a power-law $P \sim k^\gamma$ distribution, labelled with the power-law exponent and the number of cascades.

Naturally, these tweets were not uniformly distributed over time. Figure 25 illustrates the frequency of misinformation dissemination identified. As can be seen for both topics, we observe bursts, followed by periods of reduced activity.

Figure 25: Number of tweets that shared Covid-19 and Environmental claims identified as being false in Portuguese and Spanish, over time. Each dot represents the number of tweets shared per day for the top shared claims from tables 13A to 13D.

The Portuguese Covid-19 misinformation claim N1 from Table 13C, *Senador Randolfe promete comendas a médicos do Amapá pelo que chamou de heróico combate à Covid-19. Detalhes: eles trataram com hidroxcloroquina, ivermectina, vitamina D e mais. Vai condecorar?*, recorded over 2,000 shares on its first day of circulation (22 May 2021). In contrast, claims N2 and N3 achieved peak engagement earlier, between 16 and 25 August 2020.

A similar temporal pattern was observed for the Spanish Covid-19 misinformation claim N1, Table 13A, *El Gobierno paraliza en Zaragoza 5.000 kilos de mascarillas para Madrid*

porque «Aduanas cierra a las 15h» This claim was shared more than 4,000 times on 1 April 2020, after which its popularity declined markedly in subsequent days.

Comparable dissemination dynamics emerged among environmental misinformation claims. We observe that collected Portuguese environmental claims (listed in Table 13D) circulated predominantly between 11 September 2020 and 18 October 2021, while the Spanish environmental claim (listed in Table 13B)—which concerned a meteorite event—began circulating on 24 January 2021, reaching its highest level of engagement on that date.

5.3 Comparative Analysis

It is common that rumours that spread on one social network also spread on others. Therefore, we compared the fake news identified through Global Claims and the hoaxes described in Section 2 of this report. Using a Large Language Model with a prompt to compare the four lists in 1 one to 1 pairs (Spanish COVID, Portuguese COVID, Spanish Environment and Portuguese Environment), the model found no matches. We then tried a fuzzy matching approach, using Levenshtein Distance, and no claims had a distance under 50.

In summary, the study reveals that misinformation in Portuguese- and Spanish-speaking contexts—particularly around Covid-19—spread widely on Twitter/X, exhibiting distinct temporal spikes, with a small number of false claims achieving substantial reach and engagement (hundreds of shares). There is sub-topic overlap between Twitter/X and Telegram (Ex. risks of vaccines), but the wording of the claims varies significantly. These findings underscore the uneven yet impactful dynamics of misinformation circulation across languages, topics, platforms, and time, emphasising the importance of cross-linguistic, thematic and multi-platform analyses in understanding how false information propagates within digital ecosystems.

6. Technical report

6.1. Data gathering from Telegram

Telegram is a communications app where several people can form “Channels” to talk through. Telegram has an interface point (API) that lets a phone number connect to a known chat. There is no direct method to crawl the channels in the app as access to unknown channels is strictly forbidden.

Telegram is a communication platform that allows users to create “channels” for group discussions. Access to these channels is provided through an application programming interface (API), which requires a phone number to connect to a known chat. However, Telegram does not offer a direct method for large-scale crawling, as the channel name is required to retrieve its messages. Consequently, for this study we relied on a curated set of 491 channels, selected by our research team in collaboration with colleagues, which were periodically crawled to extract newly available messages.

6.2. Hoax identification in the wild

We focus on three main topics and aim to search our Telegram database for related content. Since the cascade algorithm requires well-defined queries, we first need a reliable source of hoaxes to guide the search. For this purpose, we use the *Fact-checkers* section of the Iberifier website, which compiles hoaxes debunked by various fact-checking organizations. From this source, we collect both the date when each hoax was debunked and its title.

In total, we retrieved 8,256 hoaxes spanning from April 2019 to June 2025. To align with the period covered by our Telegram dataset, we then selected only the hoaxes published between 2020 and 2023 (inclusive), resulting in a final set of 4,252 hoaxes. These hoaxes cover a wide range of topics, wider than the three main topics we want to research, namely: covid, climate change and gender related issues. Therefore, the hoaxes dataset was further refined to find hoaxes of the selected themes.

In our case, we converted all 4,252 hoaxes into embeddings using Transformer-based models and stored them in a vector database. We then formulated 24 sentences or concepts representing the target theme and used them as queries to locate hoaxes near the queries in the vector space. For example, for the climate change theme, we included concepts such as “*climate change*” and “*Rising global temperatures and greenhouse gas emissions.*” The complete list of concepts used for each topic is provided in Table 14.

Table 14. Queries used to find related hoaxes and messages.

Climate Change	Gender related issues
"Climate change"	"LGTBIQ+"
"United Nations and climate change action"	"Transgender"
"IPCC reports and global warming"	"feminism",
"Greta Thunberg and youth climate activism"	"Gloria Steinem",
"Paris Agreement and international climate policy"	"Me Too movement",
"NASA climate research and satellite data"	"sexual harassment",
"Shell and fossil fuel emissions"	"International Women's Day",

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"Greenpeace campaigns against deforestation"	"Malala Yousafzai",
"EU climate goals and emissions targets"	"NOW and feminist advocacy in the U.S.",
"ExxonMobil and climate change controversy"	"Simone de Beauvoir",
"Bill Gates and climate innovation funding"	"CEDAW and women's human rights",
"Extreme weather events"	"Emma Watson and HeForShe campaign",
"Carbon footprint reduction"	"Planned Parenthood",
"Rising global temperatures and greenhouse gas emissions"	"women's reproductive rights",
	"Pride parades",
	"Laverne Cox and transgender representation",
	"Queer culture",
	"Elliot Page and transgender visibility",
	"Same-sex marriage",
	"Conversion therapy",
	"Religious views on homosexuality",
	"Legal protections for homosexual couples",
	"Discrimination against gay men in the workplace",
	"Harvey Milk and gay rights activism",

Through this approach, we identified 157 hoaxes related to climate change and 149 hoaxes concerning gender-related issues.

6.3. Message identification in the wild

As noted above, determining whether a given message conveys the same content as a hoax is not straightforward. Processing more than six million messages individually for each hoax is unfeasible. To address this challenge, we filtered the dataset to identify messages related to the target themes.

First, each channel was segmented into a set of topics, where a *topic* is defined as a group of messages discussing the same subject. This process yielded a total of 21,614 topics. For each topic, we computed an embedding and stored it in a vector database. We then applied the same set of queries used in the hoax analysis to identify topics aligned with the desired themes. Finally, we retrieved all messages belonging to the selected topics from the database.

Using this approach, we identified 40,860 messages related to climate change published by 97 channels and 52,289 messages related to gender issues published by 102 channels.

6.4 The Covid-19 case study

The procedure used to analyze the Covid-19 theme differed from that applied to climate change and gender-related issues, as we already possessed a subset of 21 channels known to contain discussions about vaccines and Covid-19. Consequently, the process was more straightforward.

Instead of employing a vector database to search for relevant messages and hoaxes, we directly compared the embedding of each topic with the embeddings of each hoax. If the distance between a topic and a hoax was smaller than the distance

between that hoax and the mean of all embeddings, we inferred that the topic addressed the hoax. Using this method, we identified 40 distinct hoaxes.

In this case, we did not filter messages, as the dataset was considerably smaller—approximately 280,000 messages.

6.5. From messages to cascades: Introducing SLICs

SLIC stands for *Semantically-linked information cascades*, which is the end result we want to achieve. We describe them as messages linked by a combination of semantic meaning and other factors. To construct them, there are several steps to be taken: 1) choosing a hoax, 2) retrieving messages relating to a hoax, 3) reranking top-k messages, 4) triangular self-similarity adjacency, 5) Pruning the triangular self-similarity graph into a cascade. We examine this process step by step.

1. Choosing a hoax / Building the query: The first step is knowing the target hoax to be tracked. The SLIC generation algorithm tracks the cascade of a single misinformation piece. It can be used for information tracking in general, but that use-case has gone untested so far. Granularity may be as coarse or wide as needed, but it is recommended to be very specific. For example: “Anthropogenic climate change is a hoax generated by big government.” is a much more effective query than, “Climate change”, “Climate change is a hoax generated by big government.” and “Anthropogenic climate change doesn’t exist”. Regular rules applied to LLMs usually extend to this method on principle, therefore negatives like “Don’t” or “Not” are usually disregarded by the algorithm. Constructing an effective query hoax requires adjusting the level of specificity desired and running through the entire pipeline.

2. Coarse grain message retrieval: First, we need the entire message database encoded as numerical representations (embeddings) to proceed with the **semantic similarity** procedure (Consult Annex 2 for details). The embeddings are used as keys, as in an archiving system, they serve as short-hand to search for any given item; therefore we need a query to compare against these keys. The query was obtained in step 1, but also needs to be transformed into an embedding.

We perform cosine similarity on each key-query pair, obtaining one score number for each pair. We desire to extract a group of messages to link them semantically, therefore the K keys with the highest scores are selected from the database and sent forward for further analysis. This is a very common step on **Information Retrieval** problems.

Technical details: The encoder used for this purpose is Qwen3-Embedding-4B¹¹, quantized to 4-bit for speed-performance tradeoff. The system prompt was: “Given a query, retrieve relevant passages that are thematically related to the query: “. No thinking tokens were used.

3. Fine grain message retrieval: Similarity search is known to be imprecise. Common practice uses a **reranking** step. Reranking is very simple, given a **small** set of keys,

¹¹ Model checkpoint: [Qwen/Qwen3-Embedding-4B](#)

extract the most relevant ones. In essence, this is almost identical to the previous step, however, the tools applied to extract reranking scores are much more computationally demanding, therefore it is often used on reduced datasets.

Reranking gets all key-query pairs and inputs them to the reranker. The reranker computes a score for each pair. Coarse grain IR required 1 execution of the encoder. Fine grain IR requires N executions of the reranker, one for each pair. In the end, the results are a group of scores for each key, where we extract the Q highest scores.

Technical details: The reranker used for this purpose is Qwen3-Reranker-4B¹², quantized to 4-bit for speed-performance tradeoff. The system prompt was: “Given a query, decide whether the query agrees with the document mutually (bidirectional): “. No thinking tokens were used.

4. Triangular self-similarity adjacency matrix: We have a group of messages that we know relate to the target hoax. Our goal is to build a cascade of information by linking these messages. This is performed in two steps. The first phase of this procedure is computing a score for each pair of messages. The result of this step will be a directed graph (a message influences another in the future) that is fully connected forward. A similarity of 0 means there is no link.

Figure 26 is a simplification of the process. First, all messages are sorted by ascending date. All pairs of messages are evaluated through the reranker algorithm (same as step 3) and their similarity scores are annotated in matrix format.

Figure 26. Triangular self-similarity adjacency matrix explanation

	Message 1	Message 2	...	Message N
Message 1	$s_{1,1}=0$	$s_{1,2}$...	$s_{1,N}$
Message 2	$s_{2,1}=0$	$s_{2,2}=0$...	$s_{2,N}$
...
Message N	$s_{N,1}=0$	$s_{N,2}=0$...	$s_{N,N}=0$

Source: Original

Furthermore, as we discussed before, similarity by itself is not enough to link messages. A simple and effective approach is to diminish similarity by a function of time. Say, for example, messages 1 and 2 are distanced by 3 days, while messages 1 is distanced from 3 by 3 years. It stands to reason that, independently of similarity, message 1 is much more influential to message 2 than message 3, as the discourse

¹² Model checkpoint: [Qwen/Qwen3-Reranker-4B](#)

has varied wildly in that time frame. This reasoning has some flaws, as messages may really have long-term influences and be re-visited, however it is robust for common day-to-day discourse, especially in the highly mutable ecosystem of social media where trends and ideas are quickly deemed obsolete.

We perform the penalty using $(\text{years} + 1)^2$. The square term is added due to the previous consideration, where social media heavily rewards immediate interactions. The choice of time-frame (years) was arbitrary, as any time-frame would work, but years provided good representations as most similarity scores by the reranker ranged between 10 and -10.

Technical details: Same configuration as step 3. This time all messages are related pairwise and obtained their similarities. For efficiency, only the upper triangle of the matrix was computed. The only computation performed was the following:

$$s_{i,j} = f_{\phi}(m_i, m_j) / (y_{i,j} + 1)^2 \quad \forall i > 0, j > 1, j > i$$

F_{ϕ} is the parametrized reranker, m_x is the selected message, y is the number of years between messages x and y .

5. Pruning the adjacency matrix to create SLICs: We already have a graph detailing the influence from one message to another. However, a fully connected graph is impossible to interpret beyond 10 or more nodes. Instead, we perform a greedy algorithm that prunes the adjacency matrix to develop a tree formed from the relationships in the graph. Thus, we develop an original algorithm to build a SLIC.

To summarize the behaviour in layman terms. We evaluate every pair of relations between messages. We begin with the first message, which we call the ‘Root’. We find all the edges that begin on this root and end outside the new graph we are building. We find the edge with the highest score, in other words, the pair of messages that have the highest similarity between them. Each step of the algorithm adds a new message to the graph until the information cascade is completed. What we optimize is this algorithm is the sum of all relationships, which we aim to maximize. This algorithm provides a fair estimation of the best cascade, i.e. the cascade that better propagates information forward with the highest possible similarity scores.

Some additional considerations. The graph visualization and the SLIC are not identical. This means that some conveniences have been taken for the sake of readability. For example, in the visualization, messages are aligned by their channel of origin, a detail we never contemplate in the SLIC construction. This is by design, as we meant to influence the algorithm with as little information as possible, and this has been similarity and time difference.

Technical details: We detail the novel algorithm here in Algorithm 1. It has $O(N^2)$, which is comparable to the self-similarity matrix creation, thus offering no more compute overhead to the process.

Algorithm 1. SLIC building algorithm

```

1  LET  $G$  be a triangular self-similarity adjacency matrix, our fully-connected graph
2  LET  $T$  be a graph with a root (the first message), representing the final SLIC
3  LET  $N$  be the side size of the matrix
4  REPEAT  $N$  times // Each Edge  $E$  in Graph  $G$ 
5       $B \leftarrow$  Empty // Will use to represent the best edge
6      FOR EACH  $E$  in  $M$  DO // Each Edge  $E$  in Graph  $G$ 
7           $U \leftarrow$  Edge  $E_{\text{origin}}$  |  $V \leftarrow$  Edge  $E_{\text{destination}}$  // A Vertex
8          IF ( $U \in T_{\text{Vertices}}$  AND  $V \notin T_{\text{Vertices}}$ ) AND ( $B$  is Empty OR  $B_{\text{weight}} <$ 
 $E_{\text{weight}}$ )
9              // Add the most similar edge that points to an unvisited
vertex.
10             THEN  $B \leftarrow E$ 
11             Remove  $B$  from  $G_{\text{Edges}}$ 
12             Add  $E_{\text{destination}}$  to  $T$ 
13             Add  $B$  to  $T$ 
14  RETURN  $T$ 

```

Concluding remarks: The developed algorithm for SLIC construction is a multi-step process with high computational demand, especially the reranking and self-similarity phases. However, they provide high-quality estimations of semantically linked cascades, which was our initial objective.

6.6. Grouping SLICs by case

An SLIC illustrates how a single hoax is distributed across channels. By analyzing a single SLIC, we can observe patterns in which some channels initiate a hoax while others act as hubs that propagate it. Using pattern mining techniques, we can analyze multiple SLICs to model how channels influence one another more generally. This is typically represented with a who-copies-who graph—a directed graph where nodes represent channels and edges indicate influence between them. Once the graph is constructed, we can apply Social Network Analysis (SNA) techniques to identify the most important nodes in the distribution process and to classify each node as either a hub or an authority (with hubs tending to aggregate hoaxes and authorities tending to initiate their distribution), among other things. This process involves two main steps: 1) Generating a who-copies-who graph by analyzing several SLICs. 2) Applying SNA techniques to analyze the graph, determine each channel’s role, and assess their importance within the network.

1. Generating a who-copies-who graph by analyzing several SLICs: Modeling a who-copies-who graph remains an open problem, and the state of the art provides several approximations. For this study, we use the **NETINF algorithm**, which frames the task as a probability maximization problem and applies a greedy method capable of scaling to networks with hundreds of thousands of nodes.

NETINF is based on the **Independent Cascade Model**, where each node in the network has a single chance to influence its neighbors with a fixed probability. To represent this probability, NETINF employs a configurable distribution that depends on the time elapsed between channels publishing a hoax—commonly modeled with a **Power-law** or **Rayleigh** distribution.

Additionally, NETINF incorporates a **default influence probability** to account for influences that occur outside the observed data (for example, when two channels pick up a hoax from an internet forum). The algorithm begins with a graph where all nodes are connected via default influences. It then iteratively replaces one default influence edge with a real influence edge. At each step, the edge selected is the one that maximizes the likelihood of observing all the SLICs in the dataset. The process finishes when a certain number of edges is added. For this study we have added edges until all the channels in the case study appear in the graph.

2. Applying SNA techniques to analyze the graph, determine each channel's role, and assess their importance within the network: A who-copies-who graph on its own is of limited use. As the number of nodes and edges grows, it becomes increasingly difficult to extract meaningful insights directly from the graph. Therefore, we rely on Social Network Analysis (SNA) techniques to identify key information. In particular, we need methods to determine the most influential accounts in the distribution process and to reduce redundant edges, making the graph more interpretable.

Centrality metrics are a core component of the SNA toolbox, providing ways to measure the importance of both nodes and edges. Since each metric emphasizes different aspects of the network, for this study we selected the **HITS algorithm** (Kleinberg 1999) for node centrality. HITS assigns both an *authority score* and a *hub score* to each node. Hubs are nodes that point to many authorities, while authorities are nodes that are pointed to by many hubs. In our who-copies-who graph, authorities represent channels that tend to initiate hoax propagation, whereas hubs represent channels that distribute hoaxes across the network.

For edges, we selected **betweenness centrality**, which measures how many shortest paths pass through a given edge. Edges with higher betweenness are more critical for holding the network together.

Using these two metrics, we designed the visualization presented in Section 3. Node color distinguishes hubs from authorities, while node size and saturation are proportional to the HITS score—larger, more saturated nodes play a more significant role in the diffusion process. Additionally, the names of the three most important hubs and the three most important authorities are displayed next to their nodes. For edges, saturation corresponds to betweenness centrality—darker arrows indicate edges that are more essential for maintaining network connectivity, which further enhances readability by effectively downplaying redundant edges.

6.7. Visualization data source metrics

The dataset used in this study comprises **491 channels** and **6,805,626 messages** collected between 2020 and 2023 (inclusive). The median number of messages scraped from each channel is **4,043**. However, the distribution is not homogeneous; instead, it follows a **power-law pattern**. The 50% of channels with the fewest messages account for only **4%** of the total messages, while the top 5% of channels account for **45%** of all messages. Notably, the maximum number of messages

scraped from a single channel is **623,344**, representing approximately **10%** of the dataset—nearly twice the total contributed by the 50% of channels with the fewest messages. A histogram of the message distribution across channels is shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27. Histogram of number of messages published by channel

Regarding the temporal characteristics of the dataset, the number of messages scraped increased each year. Specifically, **419,351 messages** were collected in 2020; **1,576,924** in 2021; **1,966,060** in 2022; and **2,571,944** in 2023. Older messages were also scraped; however, since the quantity was very small, they were discarded from the analysis.

When examining the months of publication, we observe a slight increase in message volume during spring and at the end of the year (see Figure 28A). At the weekly level, fewer messages are published during weekends compared to weekdays (see Figure 28B). Finally, analyzing the time of day, peak activity occurs in the evenings, approximately between **15:00 and 20:00** (see Figure 28C).

In addition to text, many messages also included multimedia content. The most common type was **video**, shared in **771,617 messages (≈11%)**, followed by **files** (e.g., PDF, ZIP) with **8,501 messages (>1%)**, **images** with **5,414 messages (>1%)**, and **audio** with **3,049 messages (>1%)**.

Moreover, **3,739,279 messages (≈55%)** contained a URL linking to external websites. Among these, **187,930 (≈3%)** pointed to YouTube videos, **418,525 (≈6%)** to other Telegram channels, **319,517 (≈5%)** to X (formerly Twitter), **74,210 (≈1%)** to Rumble—an online video platform positioned as an alternative to YouTube—**60,304 (>1%)** to Reddit, **24,094 (>1%)** to Facebook, **20,852 (>1%)** to Instagram, and **11,946 (>1%)** to TikTok content.

In addition to other social media platforms, some links directed to mainstream international outlets such as *The Guardian*, *BBC*, *Reuters*, *NBC News*, *ABC* (Spain), *El Mundo*, *20 Minutos*, and *MSN*, although these appeared relatively infrequently compared to other sources. By contrast, significantly larger volumes of links originated from alternative or partisan media outlets, including *The Gateway Pundit*, *Daily Mail*, *Fox News*, *Breitbart*, *RT*, *Epoch Times*, *ZeroHedge*, *Natural News*, and *Rebel News*.

Figure 28. Volume of messages published by month/day of week/hour.

6.8. Thematic clustering methodology

This approach explores the impact of thematic clustering before classification in the automated detection of narrative positions about climate disinformation in digital media. Research on disinformation detection often uses models like BERT for supervised classification, with studies with French texts (Mebdeb et. al. 2022) ; adding explainability tools (Szczepanski et. al. 2021) and using multimodal analysis of social media (Arcos et. al. 2025). This study contributes with an unsupervised clustering phase before narrative inference, using the multilingual model distiluse-base-multilingual-cased-v2 (Reimers & Gurevych 2019), which produces comparable vector representations. The study proposes a hybrid method that combines natural language processing and thematic clustering before narrative classification to improve the accuracy of the system.

The study was structured in several phases that combined collection, filtering, vectorization, thematic clustering of contents, and later narrative analysis with pretrained models. This design made it possible to explore if the use of clustering before classification improves the performance of language models in narrative detection. The methodological workflow integrates unsupervised thematic analysis with supervised semantic classification, see Figure 29.

Figure 29: Methodological scheme of the study, which combines unsupervised thematic analysis with supervised classification based on language models.

The corpus was built from two sources. First, 7,286 fake news verified by Maldita.es maldita between 2017 and 2025 were collected. From these, 50 climate fakes were selected after applying a thematic filter centered on climate topics. Second, 23,441 news articles were downloaded from MyNews news during the first four months of 2025. Using relevant keywords from the fakes, a thematic filter reduced this corpus to 3,006, and finally 1,711 were from Spanish media. The purpose was not to create an exhaustive corpus for supervised training, but to test if prior clustering can help automatic detection of narrative positions without fine-tuning.

The selected fakes were organized into two semantic groups using KMeans ($k=2$). Then the news were vectorized and projected onto the same semantic space, with extra filtering by theme and geography. Cosine similarity was used to measure closeness to the fake narratives.

For narrative classification, the model mDeBERTa-v3-base-mnli-xnli (Laurer et. al. 2022) was used. Each news item was compared with representative statements of the fake, such as “Climate change has no relation with human activity”. The categories were SUPPORT, REFUTE and IGNORE, equivalent to entailment, contradiction and neutral.

Experimental Design: The evaluation included three experimental scenarios to assess the impact of clustering and semantic filtering on classification performance:

- **Scenario A:** news with similarity ≥ 0.5 to fake narratives
- **Scenario B:** all news in the climate cluster
- **Scenario C:** the complete corpus without clustering

Manual labeling of 40 random news per scenario was used for validation. This approach enabled systematic comparison of classification accuracy across different levels of thematic organization and semantic filtering.

6.9. Stance detection methodology and data

This study evaluates in-context learning for multilingual stance detection with generative LLMs, minimizing fine-tuning. We examine how prompt design, model family, and model size affect performance across two datasets and three languages, using five prompting schemes and four instruction-tuned LLMs. Unless noted, experiments run in zero-shot settings.

All experiments were executed on a single MareNostrum 5 Accelerated node (4×NVIDIA H100 64 GB, Intel Sapphire Rapids 8460Y+, 512 GB RAM), enabling large-scale inference without fine-tuning.

Datasets: We use SemEval-2016 Task A (English) (Mohammad et. al. 2016) and the Catalonia Independence Corpus (CIC) in Catalan (CIC-CAT) and Spanish (CIC-ES) (Zotova & Agerri 2021). Both datasets contain political tweets with target topics and ground truth labels. SemEval covers five targets (Atheism - AT, Climate Change is Real - CC, the Feminist Movement - FM, Hillary Clinton - HC, and the Legalization of Abortion - LA); we evaluate on the official test split (1,249 tweets). The CIC dataset contains tweets regarding the Catalanian Independence Movement. CIC-CAT and CIC-ES each contain ~10k tweets labeled favor /against /none; we use only the test partitions (~2k tweets per language).

LLM Models Tested: We evaluate four open-source multilingual, instruction-tuned LLMs¹³ via Hugging Face¹⁴: *Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3*, *Mistral-Small-24B-Instruct-2501*, *Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct*, and *Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct*. Inference uses max sequence length 250 and greedy decoding. Prompts follow each model’s chat template; batches are left-padded, and decoded after removing the prompt prefix.

Prompting Schemes. We test five schemes: zero-shot (Kojima et. al. 2022), few-shot (Brown et. al. 2020), chain-of-thought (CoT) (Wei et. al. 2022), COLA multi-agent prompting (Lan et. al. 2024), and a modified Chain-of-Stance (mCoS) (Ma et. al. 2024). The original Chain-of-Stance method proved to be unreproducible, therefore an inspired version was created that simplified the prompts and kept the core idea of each step. Prompts are written in the dataset language (EN for SemEval; ES/CAT for CIC). We additionally run a cross-lingual condition where all prompts (and in-context examples) are translated to English.

Baselines: To contextualize LLM performance, we compare against supervised and in-context baselines. Supervised baselines include TF-IDF+SVM (Sánchez & Martín n.d.) with feature selection via Information Gain (Cover & Thomas 2005), plus fine-tuned transformer encoders (mBERT (Devlin et. al. 2019) and XLM-R (Conneau et. al. 2020)). In-context baselines include a plain zero-shot instruction (Kojima et. al. 2022) and Stance Reasoner (Taranunxhin et. al. 2024), which augments few-shot

¹³ For brevity, we refer to *Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3* as *Mistral-7B* and *Mistral-Small-24B-Instruct-2501* as *Mistral-24B*. Like-wise, *Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct* is denoted as *Qwen-7B* and *Qwen-72B-Instruct* as *Qwen-72B* throughout the article.

¹⁴ <https://huggingface.co>

prompts with premise→conclusion reasoning; for comparability we cite results from (de Landa & Agerri 2025) on SemEval-2016 and CIC.

Evaluation Metrics: Following SemEval-2016, we report the average F1 over favor and against, excluding none: $F_{avg} = (F_{favor} + F_{against})/2$. This emphasizes explicit stance expression and avoids ambiguity in none since it is rarely a truly neutral stance.

6.10. Stance Detection Pipeline with Hybrid Retrieval architecture

The stance detection pipeline follows a modular architecture that integrates multiple data sources and processing components. The system processes data through four main stages:

(1) Data Sources collect fact-checks and news articles from APIs, (2) Data Processing performs content preparation and dual indexing, (3) Retrieval System combines semantic and keyword-based search with score fusion, and (4) Analysis Engine extracts statements, classifies stance, and performs consistency analysis to contextualize results within the overall article. This process is illustrated in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Stance Detection Pipeline Architecture.

The architecture demonstrates a systematic approach where fact-checking data from the IBERIFIER consortium and news articles from MYNEWS are first processed and indexed using both vector embeddings and traditional text search methods. This dual-indexing strategy enables the hybrid retrieval system to leverage both semantic similarity and exact keyword matching. The analysis engine then processes news articles by extracting individual statements, determining their fact-checkability, retrieving relevant fact-checks, and performing stance classification. The final consistency analysis step addresses potential context loss by evaluating statement-level results within the broader article context, ensuring that articles reporting disinformation for refutation purposes are not incorrectly classified as supporting false claims.

6.11. Stance Detection Pipeline Methodology

The system is built on three core principles that address the practical challenges of automated misinformation detection in multilingual European media environments.

- **Evidence-based verification:** The pipeline compares media content directly against a database of verified fact-checks rather than relying solely on machine learning patterns. The system leverages fact-checking work completed by established fact-checking organizations that have systematically documented and verified misinformation claims. This approach ensures that assessments are based on expert human judgment rather than algorithmic pattern recognition alone. Each analysis can be traced back to specific fact-checks, providing transparency about how conclusions were reached.
- **Statement-level analysis:** To classify the article, the system breaks down articles into individual factual statements for separate analysis. This approach recognizes that news articles often contain both accurate information and problematic claims within the same text. By analyzing statements individually, the system can identify specific misleading content while preserving the context of surrounding accurate reporting. This granular approach provides more useful information for both researchers studying misinformation patterns and policymakers developing targeted responses.
- **Consistency-level analysis:** An issue raised by the statement-level analysis is context lost. For instance, sometimes articles report a disinformation piece to be able to refute it. In this scenario, if the analysis is solely statement-level, it will be flagged as Supporting disinformation. The Consistency-level analysis allows to recontextualise the stance detection result within the overall article and give a result that is representing the overall consistency of the article rather than just the included statements.

Data processing: The pipeline handles fact-checking data from the IBERIFIER consortium fact-checking organizations¹⁵: EFE Verifica, Maldita.es, Newtral, Polígrafo, Verificat, Chequeado, and Infoveritas. Each fact-check document undergoes text extraction by concatenating title and content fields, followed by metadata extraction including keywords, formats, sources, categories, type, link, organization, and organization qualification with explanation. Documents are then split into manageable segments using RecursiveCharacterTextSplitter with configurable chunk size (1000 characters) and chunk overlap (500 characters) to preserve context across boundaries.

For enhanced analysis, each chunk is processed through an LLM (Qwen2.5-32B-Instruct) to extract structured metadata including main topic and named entities such as people, places, and organizations. The final step merges document-level metadata, chunk-level metadata (chunk index and character count), and LLM-extracted metadata into a unified structure that is then serialized for storage.

The storage process employs a dual-indexing strategy that enables both semantic and keyword-based retrieval capabilities. Text content undergoes careful segmentation into manageable chunks of approximately 1000 characters with 250-character overlaps between segments to preserve contextual relationships across boundaries. This segmentation process respects natural text structure by avoiding breaks within sentences or paragraphs, ensuring that semantic coherence is maintained throughout the chunking process.

The dual indexing architecture consists of two complementary storage systems. For semantic retrieval, chunks are processed through the Jina-v4 multilingual embedding model, which generates high-dimensional vector representations of the text content. These embeddings are normalized to unit length to ensure consistent similarity calculations and stored within a ChromaDB persistent client.

Parallel to the semantic indexing, the system creates a BM25 full-text search index using the Whoosh library¹⁶ for precise keyword-based retrieval. This index employs a straightforward schema containing unique document identifiers and stored text content, enabling traditional information retrieval methods that complement the semantic search capabilities. The Whoosh index is persisted to a configurable directory structure, allowing for efficient keyword matching and Boolean query operations.

The system incorporates sophisticated deduplication mechanisms that track previously processed document identifiers, preventing reprocessing of existing fact-checks and enabling efficient incremental updates as new fact-checking content becomes available. Comprehensive quality control measures include error handling for failed batch operations, API connection issues, JSON parsing failures, and validation errors during the metadata extraction process, ensuring robust operation across varying data quality conditions.

¹⁵(In order of appearance): verifica.efe.com/, maldita.es/, www.newtral.es/, poligrafo.sapo.pt/, www.verificat.cat/, chequeado.com/, info-veritas.com/

¹⁶github.com/mchaput/whoosh

Retrieval Methods: The system combines multiple computational approaches to improve accuracy and coverage across different types of queries and content. The dense retrieval component employs the Jina-v4 embedding model to generate multilingual vector representations that capture semantic relationships across Spanish, Portuguese, and Catalan content. ChromaDB¹⁷ serves as the vector storage system, utilizing cosine similarity calculations for retrieval of semantically related fact-checks. The system applies configurable similarity thresholds and score adjustments to ensure consistent ranking across different query types and languages.

A BM25-based retrieval layer implemented through the Whoosh library complements the dense search capabilities by providing precise keyword matching. This component serves to match exact terms. The sparse retrieval particularly benefits queries involving specific names, dates, or technical terms that require exact matching.

Dense retrieval alone faces significant limitations in disinformation detection due to the highly specific nature of false claims. Disinformation typically involves precise details about people, locations, organizations, dates, and numerical data that are crucial for accurate fact-checking. Semantic embeddings may capture general topical similarity but can miss the specific contextual elements that distinguish between similar but factually different claims. For instance, false claims about a specific politician's actions on a particular date require exact matching of these named entities, which sparse retrieval handles more effectively than semantic similarity alone. The hybrid approach ensures that both the conceptual context and the precise factual details are captured in the retrieval process.

The final retrieval step combines outputs from both dense and sparse methods using z-score normalization. This fusion approach maximizes the strengths of both retrieval methods while minimizing their individual limitations.

Statement analysis: Large language models (Qwen2.5-72B-Instruct) are used to extract potentially fact-checkable statements. Filters exclude non-factual or speculative content. Statements are evaluated for "checkability" based on specificity, verifiability, and public interest.

Stance classification A multi-step prompting approach (Chain-of-Stance reasoning) is used to classify the relation between a statement and retrieved fact-checks. Three categories are applied: supports, refutes, not related.

Classification is accompanied by transparent reasoning chains, allowing for manual control over the AI reasoning.

Technical implementation: The system operates on HPC infrastructure using SLURM-based job scheduling for distributed processing. ChromaDB provides vector storage for semantic retrieval while Whoosh implements BM25-based keyword matching. Processing throughput achieves analysis of hundreds of articles per hour with horizontal scaling across multiple compute nodes. The pipeline demonstrates

¹⁷ github.com/chroma-core/chroma

exceptional flexibility in model deployment, supporting both open-source and closed-source language models based on organizational requirements and constraints. Open-source models (such as Qwen, Llama, and Jina) can be deployed locally using vLLM¹² inference engine for complete data sovereignty and cost control. The vLLM framework provides optimized serving capabilities with features like tensor parallelism, continuous batching, and efficient memory management for high-throughput model inference. Alternatively, closed-source models (such as OpenAI GPT, Anthropic Claude) can be integrated through API endpoints for enhanced capabilities and reduced infrastructure requirements. This flexibility enables adaptation to different deployment environments, budget constraints, and data privacy requirements.

The analysis process used the HPC infrastructure at the Barcelona Supercomputing Center, and ran on 4 nodes equipped with 4x NVIDIA Hopper H100 64GB during 8 hours.

7. Conclusions

Studying social media spread patterns is a novel approach to disinformation fighting. Detecting and analysing *how*, *who* and *when* hoaxes spread across platforms is a research field still in its infancy, especially in the walled-garden ecosystem. In this regard, we have conducted a study on three common topics for disinformation (Covid, Climate change, Gender) and studied the patterns that communities adopt to spread false information.

Our first step has been to introduce a complete methodology for Telegram, flexible to other social media outlets, that relies only on content information. Traditionally, social media spread is studied using explicit links between users/messages, but this is not readily available information. Instead, this focus on content has allowed us to track down more than three hundred hoaxes and visualize their spread.

Keep in mind that our analysis is mostly done from a technical standpoint, offering insights based on data and some contextual clues. As such, one of the most glaring points of interest of this study is the heavy overlap in spread behaviour. All three topics heavily share: actors and hub/authority distribution. Many channels appear again and again across all graphs, many even unrelated to the topic; for instance, anti-vaxxers frequently post misogyny, flat-earthers are usually Covid-denialists, and so on. Overlap between topics is extremely high.

Despite each hoax having individual differences, the large-scale dynamics of propagation remains. A notable example was observed with misogyny posts, where the hoax spreads intermittently across several periods of time. Other hoaxes present very specific points in time where channels intensely cross-post in a short span. Some hoaxes have clearly defined leaders, who dominate the discourse. More disinformation dynamics can be found by analysing the fine-grain cascade graphs.

A cross-platform comparison further reinforces that while sub-topics like vaccine risks recur, the specific wording of false claims varies significantly, with no verbatim or closely-matched hoaxes found between Twitter/X and Telegram, underscoring the need for multi-platform analysis to understand the distinct yet impactful dynamics of misinformation propagation.

To conclude, this technical report aims to analyse disinformation dynamics in social media, further investigation could be performed in several ways; for instance, cleaning up visual representations of cascades, targeting known offender channels, diversifying our target social media, etc. This approach is still data-intensive, so access to social media is still a point of contention to assess the full potential of this type of technology. Our contribution to design a flexible analysis tools, despite being more versatile than before, can still be undermined by data scarcity.

8. Bibliography

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9. Annexes

Annex 1. The Digital Services Act (DSA) and Disinformation Research in the Iberian Context

As mentioned throughout the document, the current situation for online media accessibility is crucial. Here we review the recent EU regulation that addresses this issue directly.

A1.1. Background on DSA and disinformation

The Digital Services Act (Regulation (EU) 2022/2065) constitutes the European Union's most ambitious reform of digital governance since the 2000 E-Commerce Directive (European Union, 2022). It establishes a horizontal framework applicable to all online intermediaries while introducing differentiated obligations depending on the nature and scale of the service. Hosting providers and ordinary platforms must meet baseline duties, whereas Very Large Online Platforms (VLOPs) and Very Large Online Search Engines (VLOSEs), defined as those reaching more than 45 million average monthly users in the Union, are subject to more demanding requirements. In April 2023 the European Commission designated nineteen services as VLOPs/VLOSEs (European Commission, 2023a), including Google Search, YouTube, Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, and X (Twitter), which fall under direct Commission supervision

The regulation entered into force on 16 November 2022 and its implementation has been slowly taking place. Obligations specific to VLOPs and VLOSEs have been binding since August 2023, while the general regime became applicable in February 2024. Since then, the regulatory framework has entered an operational phase. The Delegated Act on data access for vetted researchers, adopted in July 2025 (European Commission, 2025b), specifies the procedures, eligibility rules, and safeguards that give effect to Article 40 on researcher access, including the creation of a dedicated DSA Data Access Portal¹⁸. This platform is already online and expected to be fully functional during the last trimester of 2025. In parallel, the Implementing Regulation on transparency reporting, related to Article 42 and adopted in November 2024 (European Commission, 2024), harmonises the structure of reports and obliges VLOPs and VLOSEs to issue them every six months from July 2025 onwards, meaning that the first ones are due in early 2026. Besides these reports, the DSA Transparency Database¹⁹ collects the reported content moderation decisions in almost real time. Naturally, while these mechanisms represent an important move toward transparency, both are at an early stage of implementation, and their practical value for the analysis of content dissemination over social networks in the Iberian context is still limited.

The DSA's enforcement is a two-fold system, shared between the European Commission, which holds exclusive supervisory powers over designated VLOPs and VLOSEs, and the Member States. At the national level, each country must appoint a Digital Services Coordinator (DSC), an independent authority responsible for supervising the intermediary services within its jurisdiction. These DSCs are endowed with powers to investigate, demand information, and impose penalties. To ensure

¹⁸ <https://data-access.dsa.ec.europa.eu/home>

¹⁹ <https://transparency.dsa.ec.europa.eu>

consistent application of the rules across the Union, all national DSCs form the European Board for Digital Services. This independent advisory group, established in early 2025 and chaired by the Commission, provides guidance and support for joint investigations. In Portugal, this role is held by the National Communications Authority (ANACOM); in Spain, the designated body is the National Commission on Markets and Competition (CNMC), although the Commission issued a formal referral in early 2025 concerning the full implementation of its supervisory powers under the Act (European Commission, 2025a).

Disinformation is addressed in the DSA within the framework of systemic risks, i.e., more general risks such as content that has negative effects for the exercise of fundamental rights, including freedom of expression and information. Articles 34 and 35 oblige VLOPs and VLOSEs to assess how their design and operation may contribute to these systemic risks, and to adopt proportionate mitigation measures. Failing to meet these obligations, platforms face sanctions of up to six per cent of their global turnover. The central innovation in relation to disinformation is the articulation between these duties and the Code of Practice on Disinformation (Ó Fathaigh et al., 2025). First launched in 2018 as a voluntary self-regulatory initiative and revised in 2022 to expand its commitments, the Code now operates under Article 45 of the DSA as a code of conduct. Signing the Code is voluntary, but once a provider adheres to it, the commitments are subject to monitoring and may be considered in assessing compliance with systemic-risk obligations. For platforms, the Code gives a clearer and easier way to demonstrate compliance with their obligations on systemic risks. At the same time, this dual approach—voluntary in the decision to join but linked to regulatory oversight once inside—illustrates both the possibilities and the difficulties of the European Union’s strategy against disinformation. It encourages responsibility without leaving behind co-regulation, and although its results will need to be seen in practice, it can be read as a positive step to advance transparency, platform accountability and the protection of fundamental rights.

A1.2. Platforms and research access

A particularly relevant aspect of the DSA for misinformation research is Article 40, which enables independent researchers to request access to non-public, proprietary data from online platforms. This provision represents an important step toward greater transparency and accountability, allowing academics to investigate how misinformation spreads, how platform algorithms shape information exposure, and how content moderation policies are applied in practice. The implementation of Article 40, coincides with significant changes in how large platforms structure access to their data, and these developments shape the methodological options available. In this regard, the European Commission has issued requests for information to several VLOPs on the design and accessibility of their research tools, signalling that questions of scope, eligibility, and functionality are central to the DSA.

In particular, platforms are expected to provide catalogues and related information, such as codebooks, changelogs and architectural documentation, so researchers know what data is available to be requested. In parallel, initiatives such as the Social

Data Science Alliance²⁰ and the DSA 40 Collaboratory²¹ aim to coordinate the scientific community in all stages of the DSA implementation, pooling resources, defining data and request taxonomies, and bringing stakeholders together to more effectively author data access applications and monitor compliance.

Different platforms have adapted their research access policies in distinct ways, reflecting varied interpretations of the new obligations. Table A1 summarises the research access available for a selection of platforms as of September 2025, with particular attention to academic research:

Meta has replaced CrowdTangle with the Meta Content Library and its API, available to vetted researchers through the ICPSR. It offers a structured environment but with scope and eligibility rules still under definition.

TikTok has opened a research API accessible to non-profit academic institutions in the European Union and the United States, while third-party services such as Tikapi provide additional, though unofficial, access pathways.

X (formerly Twitter) and Reddit reorganised their APIs in 2023, introducing paid tiers and discontinuing legacy academic-access routes; this has raised costs and reduced scale but still leaves possibilities for smaller projects or collaborations.

YouTube continues to offer its Data API, which grants access to metadata on videos and comments but not official bulk archives, and is subject to quotas and copyright restrictions.

Telegram, which is not reported as a VLOP, allows access to public channels through the Bot API and libraries such as MTPProto/TDLib and Telethon, enabling large-scale monitoring though without standardised metadata on reposts.

In addition, while not currently identified as VLOPs or VLOSEs, it is easy to argue that large language models (LLMs), such as ChatGPT, clearly fall under the scope of the DSA: they act as large-scale intermediary services, used by millions of people in the EU, and can create systemic risks—for example, by sharing false information, helping shape opinions, or influencing elections. As LLMs become part of major search engines (such as Bing with ChatGPT) and social media platforms (such as Grok on X), they potentially further increase the social impact of existing platforms, and effectively act as main gateways to information. This regulatory blind spot should be closed in the near future.

In all, the current landscape of data access provided by these VLOPs illustrates the problem of misaligned incentives between platforms and researchers - researchers often prioritize transparency and data quality, while the platforms need to protect proprietary information and the interests of their stakeholders. This issue is compounded by the asymmetry in resources between platforms and the research and NGO communities, be they financial, legal, infrastructural, or in knowledge. Researchers are expected to provide privacy and security safeguards when receiving data they might not even know exists, especially before the release of transparent data

²⁰ <https://social-data-science-alliance.org/>

²¹ <https://dsa40collaboratory.eu/>

catalogues. Moreover, there is a domain mismatch between researchers (more focused on research questions) and DSCs (more concerned with legal issues), which can further impair the process, leading to unnecessary limitations in the scope, quantity and duration of data requests.

We also note that the DSA's provisions on data access depend on who qualifies as a vetted researcher under Article 40, paragraph 4. A pilot program, led by the European Research Council and the European Commission's DG-CONNECT, has brought together regulators, researchers, DSCs and platforms, and this experience has been helping shape the future platform. It is expected that the first researchers will be vetted during 2025 and be able to complete the first request in the first semester of 2026. However, at present, this category is understood as academic or scientific institutions that meet statutory requirements, with requests evaluated by assigned (national or international) Digital Services Coordinators. Fact-checking organisations, despite being recognised in the EU Code of Practice on Disinformation as key actors in countering false content, are not automatically included. For formal NGOs, the DSA reinforces that they should have access to public data through Article 40(12) but, if they require access to non-public data, they must associate with researchers / research institutions or rely on public interfaces, transparency tools, or other partnerships. Not only does this asymmetry limit the diversity of actors who can directly benefit from Article 40 mechanisms, there is recent precedent of platforms rejecting such requests²². However, it is possible that alternative access pathways for these organisations may be explored in the future, for instance through their recognised role in monitoring the Code of Practice. The explicit legalization of alternative methods of data acquisition, including scraping, use of unofficial APIs and data donation may also help fulfill some of the needs of these organizations²³.

A1.3. Implications for disinformation research in Spain and Portugal

The gradual deployment of the DSA is beginning to shape the environment in which disinformation research takes place, although its practical contribution remains to be seen. As explained above, the most direct channel is Article 40 on data access, now specified through the delegated act adopted in July 2025. This provision establishes a formal pathway for vetted researchers to obtain non-public data from VLOPs and VLOSEs, yet, its effectiveness depends on the Digital Services Coordinators and on the implementation choices of the platforms themselves. This legal architecture offers, for the first time, a statutory basis for academic access to platform data, but also that its scope and enforcement mechanisms are still untested (Peterka-Benton, 2025).

The Transparency Database and the new six-monthly transparency reports represent a second major instrument. They provide systematic information on content moderation and recommender systems, thereby opening new opportunities for comparative

²²

<https://www.politico.eu/article/x-challenges-german-court-decision-that-would-force-it-to-share-data-with-researchers/>

²³ Mozilla has a comment on the DSA that includes these modalities: <https://www.mozillafoundation.org/en/blog/the-digital-services-act-must-ensure-public-data-for-public-interest-research/>

audits. Early studies, however, reveal inconsistencies in reporting formats and incomplete metadata, which limit their analytical utility for reconstructing disinformation dynamics in detail (Kaushal et al., 2024; Trujillo et al., 2025). Research on recommender systems also suggests that access to algorithmic explanations is too general to fully evaluate amplification patterns (Fabbri & Boratto, 2025). In short, while these transparency mechanisms advance regulatory accountability, their immediate value for empirical disinformation research is still modest.

For the Iberian context, the methodological consequences are clear. In the short term, platforms with observable public channels, particularly Telegram, continue to provide the most relevant material for analysing disinformation flows in Spain and Portugal, although the absence of explicit metadata on reposts and the opacity of cross-channel interactions requires the reconstruction of dissemination cascades, as done in the deliverable. By contrast, the restricted availability of systematic data from larger VLOPs, combined with the exclusion of fact-checking organisations from the category of vetted researchers, reinforces a structural dependence on partial datasets and heterogeneous tools. This asymmetry echoes broader concerns about the limited inclusiveness of the DSA's research provisions (Nannini, 2025).

Looking ahead, the first audit and reporting cycles scheduled for 2025–2026 are likely to refine both compliance practices and the comparability of platform data. As the first researchers get vetted and request access to platform data, it is expected that more collaborative platforms will appear, facilitating data sharing and transparency. Whether these instruments will translate into a tangible improvement for empirical disinformation research can only be evaluated after this point, but their introduction constitutes a significant step in aligning regulatory ambition with research needs.

Table A1: Research access conditions of major platforms (snapshot 2025, note that the conditions are rapidly evolving)

Platform	API availability	Data accessibility	Technical barriers	Non-technical barriers	Costs	Notes / Iberian relevance
X (Twitter) ²⁴	Paid/enterprise X API tiers; legacy academic access discontinued	Historical data available via paid tiers	Strict rate limits compared with former research tracks	Terms of service changes; evolving policies	Enterprise-grade	Previously central for propagation studies; now less accessible for academia
Meta (Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, Threads) ²⁵	Meta Content Library + API for vetted researchers	Structured access; transparency tools in parallel	Anti-scraping measures; metadata coverage incomplete	Eligibility and vetting required	No fee for vetted researchers (policy-dependent)	High relevance; access formalised but selective
YouTube ²⁶	Official Data API	Metadata on videos, channels, comments; large-scale retrieval constrained	Quotas and processing requirements; copyright considerations	Terms of service restrictions on scraping	Free (quota extensions possible)	Relevant for climate and health narratives; longitudinal capture challenging

²⁴ <https://developer.x.com/en/docs/x-api>

²⁵ <https://transparency.meta.com/es-es/researchtools/meta-content-library/>

²⁶ <https://developers.google.com/youtube/v3>

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Platform	API availability	Data accessibility	Technical barriers	Non-technical barriers	Costs	Notes / Iberian relevance
TikTok ²⁷	Research API for non-profit academics	Access via API; transparency resources; bulk retrieval subject to conditions; third-party tools such as Tikapi are not officially supported	Endpoint changes; technical obfuscation	Vetting and approvals required	Partnership/approval-based	Rapidly growing youth reach in ES/PT; highly focused on multimedia; recommendation system is very effective to increase engagement
Reddit ²⁸	Paid API since 2023 for everybody	Some third-party archives (via torrent) and tools	Rate limits and pricing barriers	ToS discourage large-scale scraping	Paid (tiered)	Smaller ES/PT footprint; relevant in niches
Telegram ²⁹	No dedicated research API; Bot API, MTPROTO/TDLIB and Telethon libraries	Public-channel content retrievable	No standardised reshare graph; cross-channel mapping difficult	Legal diligence recommended for bulk collection, which may involve processing personal data	Free	Not a VLOP; central for Iberian monitoring; feasible at scale with caveats

A1.3. Annex references

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²⁷ <https://developers.tiktok.com/products/research-api/>

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Annex 2. Technical terms

Semantic similarity: *Semantic similarity scoring* is achieved by using *semantic embeddings* to extract similarity scores through *cosine distance*. Step by step: First, a transformer converts a phrase into a numerical representation (sequence of real numbers). Using the metric known as cosine distance we can measure how different two numerical representations of texts are. Distance and similarity are inverses of each other, therefore easy to infer using any of them.

Another approach to similarity is the cross-encoder strategy, used for fine-grained retrieval. This is another transformer model that receives two sentences simultaneously and outputs a single score value. As this transformer has been trained on a similarity identification task, the cross-encoder will tell how similar both sentences are.

IBERIFIER – Iberian Digital Media Observatory

IBERIFIER is a digital media observatory in Spain and Portugal funded by the European Commission, linked to the European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO). It is made up of thirteen universities, five fact-checking organizations and news agencies, and five multidisciplinary research centers.

Its main mission is to analyze the Iberian digital media ecosystem and tackle the problem of misinformation. To do this, it focuses its research on five lines of work:

1. Research on the characteristics and trends of the Iberian digital media ecosystem.
2. Development of computational technologies for the early detection of misinformation.
3. Fact-checking of misinformation in the Iberian territory.
4. Strategic reports on threats of disinformation, both for public knowledge and for the authorities of Spain and Portugal.
5. Promotion of media literacy initiatives, aimed at journalists and informants, young people and society as a whole.

For more information, please visit the project website at iberifier.eu

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LinkedIn: [IBERIFIER](https://www.linkedin.com/company/iberifier)

Contacts

Report coordinators:

Javier Huertas (javier.huertas.tato@upm.es)

IBERIFIER coordinator:

Ramón Salaverría (rsalaver@unav.es)

www.iberifier.eu

Coordinator

Partners

Associate

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